

Fakulta rybnářství
a ochrany vod
Faculty of Fisheries
and Protection
of Waters

Jihočeská univerzita
v Českých Budějovicích
University of South Bohemia
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Quantification of food consumption of non-indigenous gobiid fish in relation to food characteristics and environmental conditions

Kvantifikace spotřeby potravy nepůvodních ryb čeledi Gobiidae ve vztahu k vlastnostem potravy a podmínkám prostředí

Doctoral thesis

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Natalia Szydłowska

Doctoral thesis by
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prostředí**

Natalia Zuzanna Szydłowska

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In Vodňany, on 26th September 2024

Supervisor:

Bořek Drozd, Ph.D.
University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice (USB)
Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW)
Research Institute of Fish Culture and Hydrobiology (RIFCH)
Zátiší 728/II, 389 25 Vodňany, Czech Republic

Consultant:

Assoc. Prof. Miloš Buřič
University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice (USB)
Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters (FFPW)
Research Institute of Fish Culture and Hydrobiology (RIFCH)
Zátiší 728/II, 389 25 Vodňany, Czech Republic

Head of Laboratory of Freshwater Ecosystems:

Assoc. Prof. Miloš Buřič

Head of CENAKVA Research Programme 4 – Freshwater ecosystems in the era of global change:

Assoc. Prof. Miloš Buřič

Dean of Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters:

prof. Tomáš Polícar

Board of doctorate study defence with reviewers:

Prof. Lukáš Kalous – head of the board
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Assoc. Prof. Josef Velíšek – board member

Assoc. Prof. Joanna Grabowska, Department of Ecology and Vertebrate Zoology, University of Lodz, Poland
– thesis reviewer

Dr. Elena Tricarico, Department of Biology, University of Florence, Italy – thesis reviewer

Date, hour and place of Ph.D. defence:

4th March 2025, 12.45 p.m., in USB, FFPW, RIFCH, Vodňany, Czech Republic

Name: Natalia Zuzanna Szydłowska

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CHAPTER 1

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

1.1. Ponto – Caspian region: prominent donor area of non-native species in Europe

Biological invasions continue to pose one of the most significant current threats to the world's functional, biological, and genetic diversity (Dudgeon et al., 2006; Keller et al., 2011; Shuai et al., 2018; Roy et al., 2023), with freshwater ecosystems being the most affected (Bernery et al., 2022). The global scale of this issue is evident in the increasing number of newly established non-native species, driven by ongoing globalization (Seebens et al., 2017, 2021), environmental homogenization (McKinney and Lockwood, 1999; Olden and Poff, 2004; Olden and Rooney, 2006; Rahel, 2008), and accelerating global warming (Huang et al., 2011; Hesselschwerdt et al., 2018). Once introduced, these non-indigenous species can disrupt native ecosystems by altering food webs (Munawar et al., 2005), hybridizing with native species, and/or spreading pathogens (Vitule et al., 2009), thereby causing significant impacts on ecosystem functioning (Gozlan et al., 2010; Strayer, 2010; Simberloff et al., 2013; Pyšek et al., 2020; Ricciardi et al., 2021).

In recent decades, the Ponto-Caspian region has emerged as a notable source of freshwater species introductions throughout Europe (Rakauskas et al., 2018; Soto et al., 2023), including invertebrates and fishes, which, due to human activities, successfully expanded their native distribution and penetrated the new localities (Ojaveer et al., 2002). They were mainly introduced out of the native region by human-derived activities, either directly, e.g. by ballast water transport via vessels (Jude et al., 1992; Sapota, 2004; van Beek, 2006; Hempel and Thiel, 2013), as well as aquaculture and angling related activities (Tricarico, 2012; Sicuro et al., 2016; Carpio et al., 2019), or indirectly, combined with a common high natural migration ability of non-native freshwater invaders through one of three main ecological corridors formed based on European rivers basins interconnections (Figure 1) (Bij de Vaate et al., 2002). Each of the pathways covers routes along the Volga (northern corridor) (Grabowska et al., 2008; Głowaciński et al., 2011), Dnieper (central corridor) (Jążdżewski et al., 2002; Rizevsky et al., 2007) and Danube (southern corridor) (Maclsaac et al., 2001; Copp et al., 2005) rivers, respectively. One of the most representative fish groups originating from the Ponto-Caspian area are gobiids (Gobiidae, Actinopterygii) (Neilson and Stepien, 2009). At least five species have established populations in European inland freshwater ecosystems and settled permanently there, i.e., the bighead goby – *Ponticola kessleri* (Günther, 1861) (Neilson and Stepien 2009), the monkey goby – *Neogobius fluviatilis* (Pallas, 1814), the racer goby – *Babka gymnotrachelus* (Kessler, 1857), the western tubenose goby – *Proterorhinus semilunaris* (Pallas, 1814) and the round goby – *Neogobius melanostomus* (Pallas, 1814) (Copp et al., 2005).

Figure 1. The migration corridors of the Ponto-Caspian freshwater species in Europe proposed by Bij de Vaate et al. (2002).

1.2. Round goby: a model invasive fish from the Ponto-Caspian region

The round goby, *Neogobius melanostomus* (Pallas 1814), is a prominent example of an invasive aquatic fish species, extensively studied in both laboratory and field settings in recent decades (Cerwenka et al., 2023). First recorded outside its native range in 1990 in the Gulf of Gdansk (Skóra and Stolarski, 1993), it has rapidly formed dense populations (Corkum et al., 2004; Johnson et al., 2005) across regions from North America's Great Lakes (Jude et al., 1992; Ricciardi and Maclsaac, 2000) to various Central and Western European rivers (Jurajda et al., 2005; Piria et al., 2011; Manné et al., 2013; Roche et al., 2015) and areas around the Baltic Sea (Azour et al., 2015; Quattrocchi et al., 2023).

The round goby's success as an invasive species is linked to traits that facilitate colonization across both sides of the Atlantic (Corkum et al., 2004; Olden and Rooney, 2006; Kornis et al., 2012). Key biological factors include early sexual maturation, a shorter lifespan, and smaller adult size (Simonović et al., 2001; Gutowsky and Fox, 2012; Masson et al., 2018). Its reproductive strategy involves multiple spawning events per year (Kulikova and Fandeeva, 1975), parental care (Sapota, 2004), and aggressive behavior (L'avrinčikova and Kováč, 2007), all of which support its successful establishment in new environments.

Interestingly, recent studies revealed that the expanded innate immune system of the round goby might contribute to its successful settlement as well (Adrian-Kalchhauser et al., 2020). Moreover, it exhibits high tolerance range towards different environmental conditions, due to which owes successful spread and establishment in both freshwater as well as marine ecosystems (Charlebois et al., 2001; Erős et al., 2005). Such adaptability is reflected in relatively low species requirements towards wide-ranging environmental conditions, e.g., salinity (Karsiotis et al., 2012; Behrens et al., 2015; Puntila-Dodd et al., 2021), oxygen concentration (Behrens et al., 2017; Krabbenhoft and Kashian, 2022), or water temperature (Cross and Rawding, 2009; Christensen et al., 2021; Nikel et al., 2021). Given to that, even

heavily polluted areas are intensively colonised by this species (Vélez-Espino et al., 2010; McCallum et al., 2017; Kovyrshina and Rudneva, 2018). Moreover, the ability of non-native species to establish themselves and spread in new environments frequently hinges also on their capacity to utilize food resources within the invaded ecosystem. This is often accomplished through flexible feeding behaviour and the ability to swiftly adapt to new conditions (Diggins et al., 2002; Carman et al., 2006; Copp et al., 2008). The invasive round goby, in particular, can notably alter food web structures by preying directly on macroinvertebrate assemblages (Barton et al., 2005; Krakowiak and Pennuto, 2008; Kornis et al., 2012; Mikl et al., 2017a; van Deurs et al., 2021).

1.3. Feeding ecology of the round goby

Overall, Ponto-Caspian gobies are recognized as opportunistic feeders (Kostrzewa and Grabowski, 2003; Grabowska et al., 2023), adapting their diet based on the most abundant and available prey in their environment (Carman et al., 2006). Thus, depending on the locality, they can predominantly consume molluscs (in lentic waters) to almost exclusively feed on other macrozoobenthos groups, such as e.g. amphipods in lotic waters, respectively (Kornis et al., 2012; Brandner et al., 2013). These geographic and habitat differences significantly shape their diet, leading to variations such as feeding on chironomids, trichopterans, bivalves, and amphipods in the wetlands of the Caspian Sea (Abdoli et al., 2012), to consuming up to 76 different taxa in areas outside their native range (Dashinov and Uzunova, 2020).

The round goby is an omnivorous fish which exhibits a highly variable diet influenced by environmental conditions and habitat characteristic (Števo ve and Kováč, 2013; Perello et al., 2015; Oesterwind et al., 2017). However, the primary food sources are represented by macrozoobenthos assemblages which are under constant feeding pressure (Phillips et al., 2003; Adámek et al., 2007; Perello et al., 2015; Nurkse et al., 2016; Oesterwind et al., 2017; 2018; Dashinov and Uzunova, 2020). The extent of predation impact varies based on factors such as fish size, season, habitat, and the availability of specific prey items (Diggins et al., 2002; Polačik et al., 2009; Števo ve and Kováč, 2016). Accordingly, significant macrozoobenthos populations decline was observed in numerous localities. For instance, in Lake Michigan (North America), the round goby occurrence resulted in intensified foraging on dreissenids, isopods, amphipods, trichopterans (Barton et al., 2005; Lederer et al., 2008), while in the Dyje River system (Central Europe), a significant decline in annelids, bivalves, gastropods, crustaceans, ephemeropterans, dragonflies and chironomids abundance were observed, respectively (Barton et al., 2005; Mikl et al., 2017).

Moreover, the round goby has significantly impacted indigenous fish populations through predation on eggs and juveniles, although its primary diet does not heavily rely on these components (Roseman et al., 2006). Studies suggested that its effect on native fish is more due to competition than direct predation (Vašek et al., 2014). However, predation on fish eggs and fry may vary based on locality and habitat structure, with higher predation noted in artificially transformed environments compared to specimens from natural shores with gravel bottoms (Saedi et al., 2017). These differences might be due to the lack of availability of other food items, in line with the generalist feeding behaviour of the round goby, which adapts and preys on accessible resources (Skóra and Rzeznik, 2001; Kornis et al., 2012). Research indicates that in controlled conditions, the round goby may consume fish eggs if no other food is available, but in natural settings, eggs are a secondary choice (Fitzsimons et al., 2006). Significant predation impacts of the round goby upon other fish have been observed, e.g. in lake trout *Salvelinus namaycush* (Walbaum, 1792) and rainbow trout *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (Walbaum, 1792), where round goby presence has hindered restoration efforts

(Chotkowski and Marsden, 1999; Fitzsimons et al., 2006). Similarly, predation on fish has also been documented in smallmouth bass offspring *Micropterus dolomieu* Lacepède, 1802 (Steinhart et al., 2004a), and Atlantic herring *Clupea harengus* Linnaeus, 1758, primarily by smaller (<10 cm) goby individuals (Wiegleb et al., 2018). DNA-based gut content analysis also confirmed round goby predation on the common nase *Chondrostoma nasus* (Linnaeus, 1758) at natural spawning sites, posing potential conservation issues for cyprinid rheophilic species as well (Lutz et al., 2020). However, despite these records, fish eggs and fry generally remain a supplementary part of the round goby diet (Janssen and Jude, 2001; Mychek-Londer et al., 2013).

Moreover, due to evident opportunistic feeding strategy, the round goby can dominate in exploiting the food resources and can outcompete the native local species while diet overlaps, increasing competition among native species (Dubs and Corkum, 1996; Karlson et al., 2007; Ustups et al., 2016). Firth et al. (2021) have demonstrated a visible increase in the diet overlap occurrence among native benthic fish species following the arrival of the round goby within the Laurentian Great Lakes ecosystem, leading to notable changes in fish species composition and population structure (Bergstrom and Mensinger, 2009; Skabeikis, 2019; McAllister et al., 2022).

Overall, the round goby's diet undergoes significant shifts with size, age, and environmental conditions (Kornis et al., 2012). Juveniles primarily consume soft-bodied prey such as chironomid larvae, while adults increasingly feed on hard-bodied prey like molluscs and crustaceans, facilitated by their robust molariform teeth adapted for such diets (Jennings et al., 2001; Andraso et al., 2011). Seasonal changes also influence their diet, with chironomids being more prevalent in spring, and amphipods and molluscs dominating in summer and autumn (Borza et al., 2009). Additionally, the round goby's feeding habits vary throughout the diel basis (Carman et al., 2006), where in case of juveniles shift from benthic prey during daylight to pelagic prey at night, supporting their vertical migration and colonization abilities (Hensler and Jude, 2007; Olson and Janssen, 2017). Factors such as pollution and water depth significantly affect diet composition in the round goby, with less varied diets and decreased feeding activity in polluted areas (McCallum et al., 2017), and different prey selections at various depths (Schaeffer et al., 2005). Furthermore, diet and feeding behaviour can differ between sexes (Thompson and Simon, 2014), as males often exhibit lower gut fullness during the spawning season due to reduced feeding activity and nest guarding (Všetičková et al., 2015). These variations are closely linked to specific study areas, where differing proportions and patterns have been observed.

1.4. Quantification methods for food consumption

In order to assess the predatory pressure and potential impact of the round goby on locally available prey assemblages, it is necessary to incorporate quantification methods into research activities. However, up to date, research on predatory habits of the round goby has predominantly utilized descriptive methods like gut content analysis, which offers only limited insights into its ecological niche and food preferences in specific regions following different indices (Amundsen et al., 1996; Marsden et al., 1996; Števove and Kováč, 2016; Dashinov and Uzunova, 2020). While these studies have highlighted the importance of certain taxa in the goby's diet (Kuhns and Berg, 1999; Barton et al., 2005; Polačik et al., 2009; Kirilenko and Shemonaev, 2012; Mikl et al., 2017a; van Deurs et al., 2021), but at the same time they can lead to overstate the importance of indigestible prey (Baker et al., 2024). Following that, in order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the round goby's dietary behaviour, advanced methods have been developed. These are, for instance, DNA analysis

techniques utilising polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and specific primers to detect DNA of prey items in fecal samples of predator, providing a clear picture of diet composition (Corse et al., 2010; Wallin Kihlberg et al., 2023). Additionally, stable isotope analysis (SIA) offers broader insights into the species' dietary history, trophic position, niche width, and potential competition (Boecklen et al., 2011). SIA has been proven valuable in assessing the predation and competition pressures exerted by invasive species in ecosystems (Balzani and Haubrock, 2022).

Further methods aiming at the quantification of prey consumption and thus the predatory impact of a species (Elliot and Persson, 1978; Durbin et al., 1983) include indirect methods based on bioenergetic models (Karjalainen et al., 1997; Hartman and Hayward, 2007). Several studies in the Great Lakes have already developed bioenergetic models to understand the impact of the invasive round goby (Lee and Johnson, 2005; Johnson et al., 2005). Even though these models have provided valuable insights into the trophic pathways and relationships between prey and predator fish populations, e.g. evidence of increased predation by predatory species and its possible calculated pressure within the annual scale (Madenjian et al., 2011), still these predictive models are often considered less reliable compared to direct measurement methods (Bromley, 1994).

To obtain precise estimates of predatory impact, direct methods that measure daily food intake *in situ* are crucial (Sun et al., 2016). These involve examining stomach or gut fullness to estimate prey consumption, adjusted by the evacuation rate (R), which measures the mass of food expelled over time (Talbot, 1985; Bromley, 1994). Since the evacuation rate primarily regulates feeding rate (Hedden et al., 2021), understanding it is essential for accurate diet evaluation. Although both methods have drawbacks, *in situ* estimates are more reliable (Bajkov, 1935; Elliott and Persson, 1978; Richter et al., 2018), and applied under field conditions (Worischka and Mehner, 1998), with fewer assumptions required (Bartell et al., 1986). Accurate evacuation rates prevent misjudging digestible versus indigestible foods, which snapshot stomach content analyses can distort (Gerking, 1994; MacNeil et al., 2001; Lagrue and Bollache, 2006; Baker et al., 2024).

While evacuation rate approach is frequently employed to determine daily intake or ratio of species in aquaculture (Storebakken et al., 1999; Handeland et al., 2008; Dürrani and Seyhan, 2019), it can also be successfully applied to achieve a more precise evaluation of the direct ecological impact of non-native fish species on food webs by its direct exerts predation in the wild (Hedden et al., 2021).

1.4.1. Gut evacuation rate: effect of abiotic conditions

In fish the passage of food through the gastrointestinal tract can be influenced by numerous variables (Bromley, 1994). Depending on the character of the studies, there can be taken into account a variety of factors, e.g., gut content volume (Elliott, 1991), food composition including its nutritional value (Andersen, 1999; Adamidou et al., 2009), content of ash, chitin (Andersen et al., 2016) or lipid (Bureau et al., 2003) in tissues, as well as meal size (Sveier et al., 1999; Andersen, 1998), respectively. Nevertheless, the majority of performed studies have shown that temperature, prey type and predator size, should be considered the most common and relevant factors (Noble, 1973; Garber, 1983; Mills et al., 1984; Karjalainen et al., 1991; Temming and Andersen, 1992; Bromley, 1994; Pääkkönen and Marjomäki, 1997; Temming et al., 2002; Gillum et al., 2012).

Temperature represents one of the most studied environmental factors in terms of gastric evacuation rate in numerous fish species (Shrable et al., 1969; Edwards, 1971; Persson, 1979; Pääkkönen and Marjomäki, 1997; Sweka et al., 2004; Gillum et al., 2012; Redd, 2015;

Bascinar et al., 2016; Horstman, 2020). The functioning of fish as an ectotherm (poikilotherm) organism is conditional upon thermal conditions changes (Volkoff and Rønnestad, 2020). Accordingly, temperature controls various processes, including metabolic rate (Brett, 1970) and, consequently, energy balance (Liu et al., 2019). Fish growth rate and physiology are also recognized as temperature-dependent processes (Wu et al., 2015). Overall, the temperature effect might be reflected in feeding strategy changes by intensified or reduced food intake (Kinne, 1960; Hidalgo et al., 1987), which consequently leads to digestion process alterations, including nutrient absorption efficiency due to changed digestive enzyme activities process and subsequently gut evacuation rate (GER) and time (GET) (Persson, 1979, 1981; Dos Santos and Jobling, 1992).

In general, evacuation rate is considered to be positively linearly dependent on temperature, where GER is accelerated by increasing temperature (Elliott, 1972; Steigenberger and Larkin, 1974; Hofer et al., 1982; Persson, 1982; Singh-Renton and Bromley, 1996; Legler et al., 2010; Stehlik et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2015; Horstman, 2020). However, the general pattern is violated in some studies, i.e. fish exhibit either significantly higher evacuation rates in the lower temperatures, confirming the negative correlation of GER with the temperature (Nagel et al., 2011), or GER is even recognised as temperature independent process (Mychek-Londer and Bunnell, 2013).

Further environmental conditions and their effects on evacuation rates in fish which were given upon testing, included salinity (Vinagre et al., 2007; Noor et al., 2018), or the oxygen level (Chabot et al., 2015; Fitzgibbon et al., 2010), however they are still in minority while focusing on abiotic effects of the total gut clearance.

1.4.2. Gut evacuation rate upon biotic factors

While considering the biotic factors, gut evacuation rate may vary considerably with predator as well as prey characteristics (Bromley, 1994). As one of the main is recognised the prey type (Jones, 1974; MacDonald et al., 1982). Gut evacuation rate can even differ in taxonomically closed prey taxa, predominantly depending on body wet weight (Bromley, 1994), but also origin (Van der Lingen, 1998), body structure (Singh-Renton, 1990; dos Santos and Jobling, 1992; Andersen et al., 1999) and even physico-chemical properties of prey (Bureau et al., 2003; Aas et al., 2011; Andersen et al., 2016) should be taken into consideration in predator's GER estimation. Following that, we can distinguish two main groups of prey types, i.e. soft-bodied versus hard-bodied prey, where additional body support in the form of exoskeleton plays crucial role as a barrier for digestive juices, which is subsequently resulted in slower digestion process (Bromley, 1994).

Another biotic variable related to prey characteristic influencing the evacuation rate is the size of the food particle or prey individuals, respectively (Bromley, 1994). However, the studies focusing on prey size provide a number of contradictory statements (Swenson and Smith, 1973; dos Santos and Jobling, 1991) regarding the relationship between gut evacuation rate and prey size. Majority of performed experiments have shown positive correlation between them (Windell, 1967; Bagge, 1977; dos Santos and Jobling, 1995; Andersen, 1998). Nevertheless, studies focused on ration size supplied to the largemouth bass – *Micropterus salmoides* (Lacepède, 1802), revealed negative correlation, i.e. time of gut evacuation process increased with the prey portion size (Beamish, 1972). But in case of the whiting – *Merlangius merlangus* (Linnaeus, 1758) fed by three different food sizes, the effect of prey size on GER have not been proven (Bromley, 1988; Andersen, 1999), similar to the turbot – *Scophthalmus maximus* (Linnaeus, 1758) where both variables were recognized as mutually uncorrelated (Bromley, 1987).

1.5. Predator-prey interaction

1.5.1. Round goby: an invader turned prey

Upon entering new ecosystems, a role of the round goby in the invaded localities is not limited solely to predation on other biotic components of the ecosystem, but simultaneously itself becomes a significant food resource for a variety of local predatory fish species (Jacobs et al., 2010; Taraborelli et al., 2010; Lenhardt et al., 2011). The round goby thus became a mesopredator (lower-ranking predator) in the invaded ecosystem, i.e. predator whose populations are controlled by a higher-ranking predator (apex or top predator) (Ritchie and Johnson, 2009). According to Hirsch et al. (2016), the main fish predators of the round goby can be found in four primary groups: a) native benthic fishes, b) predatory gadids, c) percids and basses, d) salmonids and whitefishes. Following that, the mottled sculpins – *Cottus bairdii* (Girard, 1850) represent the native benthic species recognised to predate on young of the year (YOY) of the round goby (French and Jude, 2001). However, the most significant gadid, possessing a potential to effectively control the round goby in freshwaters, is the burbot – *Lota lota* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hensler et al., 2008; Stapanian et al., 2011; Jacobs et al., 2010; Kundruhn, 2014; Hares et al., 2015; Mikl et al., 2017b). However, a degree of predation pressure of the burbot towards the round goby seems to be remarkably influenced by both ecosystem conditions and the predator size, with larger and older burbot being more effective predators than their younger and smaller counterparts (Madenijan et al., 2011). Interestingly, Hensler et al. (2008) noted that a diet predominantly consisting of the round goby can actually restrict burbot growth, as those with a high goby intake showed significantly slower growth compared to those with a more varied diet. Additionally, the round goby is effectively utilised in the marine ecosystems as well. It has become a crucial part of the diet of the Atlantic cod – *Gadus morhua* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the Baltic Sea, often making up over 50% of the cod diet, irrespective the cod size or the depth of the inhabited water (Almqvist et al., 2010; Pachur and Horbowy, 2013; Funk et al., 2021).

Nevertheless, one of the most extend fish group actively feeding on non-native round goby are percids. The European perch – *Perca fluviatilis* (Linnaeus, 1758) is considered as a percid effectively utilizing the round goby in both freshwater as well as brackish ecosystems (Almqvist et al., 2010; Rakauskas et al., 2013; Mikl et al., 2017b). In the Baltic Sea, the round goby constitutes a major part of the perch diet, making up between 52% and 83% of the overall diet composition. The proportion of round goby in the total perch diet predominantly varies according to habitat characteristics (Liversage et al., 2017). Similarly, a high predation rate on round goby has been observed in adults of the yellow perch – *Perca flavescens* (Mitchill, 1814) (Campbell et al., 2009; Taraborelli et al., 2010; Crane et al., 2015), which are aided by consumption of this invasive species to optimize foraging efforts due to high goby abundance in invaded waters (Johnson et al., 2005; Campbell et al., 2009; Reyjol et al., 2010; Taraborelli et al., 2010; Crane et al., 2015). Moreover, the round-goby based diet is linked to improved nutritional states in yellow perch, reflected by increased body mass and length (Crane et al., 2015). Furthermore, the round goby is also actively fed by pikeperches/zanders (genus *Sander*) worldwide. The pike-perch – *Sander lucioperca* (Linnaeus, 1758) feeds on the round goby once it achieves a length of over 200 mm (Hempel et al., 2016). In the sauger – *Sander canadensis* (Griffith and Smith, 1834) the round goby can compose up to 65% of the total diet content (Reyjol et al., 2010), whereas in the walleye – *Sander vitreus* (Mitchill, 1818), its proportion in the gut content ranges from 10% in Lake Erie (Johnson et al., 2005) to up to 50 % in Lake St. Pierre in the St. Lawrence River (Reyjol et al., 2010), respectively.

Moreover, the exerted predation on the round goby by the smallmouth bass – *M. dolomieu* is more pronounced in areas where both species have coexisted for extended periods. This increased predation on the round goby is likely due to the bass developing a learned behaviour for gobies hunting (Steinhart et al., 2004b; Reyjol et al., 2010; Brownscombe and Fox, 2013). The round goby also forms a part of the diet in the largemouth bass – *Micropterus salmoides* (Lacepède, 1802) (Taraborelli et al., 2010).

As regards salmonids and whitefishes, the round goby was found as prey in two species: the lake trout *Salvelinus namaycush* (Walbaum, 1792) and the lake whitefish *Coregonus clupeaformis* (Mitchill, 1818). However, the round goby importance as a food item in these fishes varies among the ecosystems (Hirsch et al., 2016). Therefore, depending on locality, the round goby may be classified as a minor (Jacobs et al., 2010), secondary (Happel et al., 2018) or even dominant (Dietrich et al., 2006; Rush et al., 2012; Roseman et al., 2014; Luo et al., 2019) food item in the lake trout diet. Nevertheless, in the lake whitefish, the round goby represents relatively new prey item, whose importance is strictly correlated with the season (Lehrer-Brey and Kornis, 2014), which significantly changes throughout the year depending on the lake locality region (Pothoven and Madenjian, 2013).

Furthermore, considering the local European scale and predation risk posed by native higher predators, the European eel – *Anguilla anguilla* (Linnaeus, 1758) appears to successfully prey on the round goby based on our field observations. Although specific studies on the direct eel predation on the round goby are limited, some reports indicate that eel populations appear to be increased following the introduction and proliferation of the round goby (Janač et al., 2019). Therefore, further research, including laboratory studies, is needed to confirm predation of the European eel on the round goby (Franta, 2024; Franta et al., 2024; Szydłowska et al., 2024).

1.5.2. Early higher predator risk detection: possible impact on fish foraging activity and feeding efficiency

In our pursuit of understanding prey-predator interactions at multiple levels in the invaded ecosystems and how these interactions influence the food resource exploitation by the round goby, it is essential to highlight the importance of early detection of predation risk as a key survival skill for prey species (Berejikian et al., 2003; Sih et al., 2010). Foraging animals detect and respond to various stimuli, including stress signals that arise from predator-prey encounters (Hettyey et al., 2015).

The reliance on chemical communication in predator-prey interactions is particularly pronounced in aquatic systems, where water effectively transmits these cues over distances (Ward and Mehner, 2010). This form of communication is regarded as one of the most universal, particularly advantageous in environments where visual signals are compromised—such as in low-light conditions, turbid waters, or structurally complex habitats—settings that make visual predator detection challenging (Giske et al., 1994; Bryer et al., 2001; Alemadi and Wisenden, 2002). Following that, extensive research has documented the importance of chemical signals for assessing risks and avoiding predators (Smith, 1986; Chivers and Smith, 1998; Kats and Dill, 1998; Ferrari et al., 2010). In these interactions, both predators and prey release specific chemical indicators: predators emit kairomones and digestion-related signals (Ocasio-Torres et al., 2021), while prey releases alarm cues, either heterospecific (Golub et al., 2005) or derived from conspecific through skin damage caused by injuries from the predator's feeding activity (Brown, 2003). Additionally, disturbance cues, which are intraspecific signals released in response to perceived threats and stress, serve as important warning mechanisms for nearby individuals (Bairos-Novak et al., 2019; Goldman et al., 2020; Crane et al., 2021). Together, these chemical cues play a critical role in alerting other organisms to predation

risks in the environment (Chivers and Smith, 1998; Burks and Lodge, 2002; Brown, 2003; Wisenden, 2003; Barcellos et al., 2011; Miyai et al., 2016), however, the effectiveness of these signals can be diminished by chemical pollutants derived from human activities, increasingly prevalent in many aquatic ecosystems (Fisher et al., 2006; Kümmerer, 2008; Olsén, 2014; Donk et al., 2016). In contrast, in the sensory hierarchy of some fish species, such as certain gobiids (Gobiidae, Actinopterygii), visual perception might play a more significant role (Utne-Palm, 2001). This could be due to the variation in chemical cue production in their epidermis (Pfeiffer, 1977; Pütys et al., 2015), with some gobiids lacking alarm substance cells. Furthermore, the presence of club cells responsible for the chemical substance secretion in the skin does not necessarily ensure a response to chemical alarm signals (Smith, 1992; Marsh-Hunkin et al., 2012).

Overall, exposure to danger-acquiring signals triggers anti-predatory behaviours unique to each species, which in turn improve survival rate in prey organisms (Brown, 2003; Brown and Chivers, 2006). While following that, such signals can influence overall fish fitness-related activities, notably feeding behaviour (Houston et al., 1993). These effects can be manifested in prey organisms by changes in the balance between feeding and hiding behaviour (Pettersson and Brönmark, 1993; Lehtiniemi, 2005), reduced food consumption in response to predator-derived chemical cues (Kristensen and Closs, 2004; McCormick and Larson, 2007; McCormick and Manassa, 2008; Palacios et al., 2016; Palacios and McCormick, 2021), and they can even lead to periods of complete feeding cessation (Foam et al., 2005; Sanches et al., 2015; Arvigo et al., 2019).

1.6. Objectives of the thesis

The primary aim of the present Ph.D. thesis was to assess the gut evacuation rate in the laboratory, taking into account food characteristics as well as environmental conditions, such as abiotic factors (e.g., thermal conditions) and the presence of higher predators, which were simulated using different chemical and visual stimulants. This research provides a comprehensive dataset for calculating consumption rates of individual prey types/species, offering accurate evaluations of the predation pressure exerted by the highly invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) on invaded ecosystems. Coupled with the gut samples from the field, these assessments can be used to calculate and quantify the food consumption of the round goby in the locally invaded ecosystem. To obtain more accurate and applicable outcomes that might reflect natural conditions more precisely, we also included tests of gut evacuation rate and feeding activity under the effect of an array of abiotic and biotic factors that can influence round goby diet and feeding efficiency and, thus, predatory pressure on local macrozoobenthic assemblages.

The specific objectives were:

1. To assess gut evacuation rate in the round goby under laboratory conditions to observe how food processing differs depending on the type of prey (hard-bodied versus soft-bodied prey), temperature conditions over season (summer versus autumn), and prey availability (limited prey availability in non-continuous feeding mode versus continual feeding with multiple prey types) (**Chapter 2**).
2. To determine a general speed of gut evacuation rates in the round goby and compare these rates with those already reported for local native species/counterparts in literature to assess the potential efficiency and superiority of the round goby in this trait over native ones (**Chapters 2 and 3**).

- 3 To investigate a potential non-consumptive effect of the presence of the native apex predator (European eel - *Anguilla anguilla* and European perch - *Perca fluviatilis*) upon feeding activity and food processing efficiency of the non-native mesopredator – round goby (**Chapter 3 and 4**).
4. To obtain the insights into the early risk detection abilities of the invasive mesopredator – round goby in order to assess which type of stimuli (chemical cues or visual stimuli) takes the prevalence in the recognition of the predation presence by higher predator (**Chapters 3 and 4**).

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CHAPTER 2

GUT EVACUATION RATE AS A TOOL FOR REVEALING FEEDING PATTERNS IN THE INVASIVE ROUND GOBY (*NEOGOBIUS MELANOSTOMUS*) UNDER DIFFERENT FEEDING MODES, FOOD TYPES AND TEMPERATURES

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Research Article

Gut evacuation rate as a tool for revealing feeding patterns in the invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) under different feeding modes, food types and temperatures

Natalia Z. Szydłowska¹, Marek Let¹, Pavel Franta¹, Miloš Buřič¹, Susanne Worischka^{2,3}, Luise Richter^{4,5}, Bořek Drozd¹

¹ South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Zátěží 728/II, 389 25 Vodňany, Czech Republic

² University of Koblenz, Institute for Integrated Natural Sciences, Universitätsstr. 1, 56070 Koblenz, Germany

³ Federal Institute of Hydrology, U4 Animal Ecology, Am Mainzer Tor 1, 56068 Koblenz, Germany

⁴ Institute of Hydrobiology, Technische Universität Dresden, 01062 Dresden, Germany

⁵ Wasserwirtschaftsamt Hof, Jahnstraße 4, 95030 Hof, Germany

Corresponding author: Natalia Z. Szydłowska (nszydłowska@frov.jcu.cz)

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Abstract

The round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) is a well-known invasive fish. Knowledge of its feeding habits and means of food processing is key in understanding its impact on aquatic food webs. The present study assessed the gut evacuation rate of round gobies feeding on three different types of prey occurring naturally in the diet of this species (small native freshwater clams, an invasive amphipod and chironomid larvae), at two different temperatures (14 and 20 °C) and under different food availability scenarios (continuous and non-continuous feeding). Gut evacuation rates varied significantly between the prey availability scenarios and, specifically, round gobies processed prey significantly faster in the continuous feeding mode when food was regularly available than when fed only once. The highest evacuation rates were detected for individuals fed with clams, in which complete gut clearance was observed within 16 h, compared to within 24 h and 36 h for chironomid larvae and amphipods, respectively. Our study shows that round gobies evacuate chironomid and mollusc prey most rapidly, which suggests that potentially the highest predatory pressure will be exerted on these prey types, assuming that all three prey species are locally present. The slower processing and digestion of amphipods may be due to their bulkier shape, which makes them more difficult to swallow. The relatively high evacuation efficiency of the round goby observed in the continuous feeding mode suggests overall increased pressure on food resources, thereby potentially reducing availability for other consumers and accelerating resource depletion, mainly driven by the high local densities of the round goby populations.

Key words: intestine clearance, prey consumption, predatory impact, non-indigenous species, prey availability

Introduction

Non-native invasive species are commonly regarded as one of the greatest contemporary threats to the functional, biological and genetic diversity of the world's biota (Dudgeon et al. 2006; Keller et al. 2011; Shuai et al. 2018). Both the magnitude of this problem and the number of newly established non-indigenous species continue to increase as a result of constant globalisation (Seebens et al. 2017, 2021), environmental homogenisation (McKinney and Lockwood 1999; Olden and Poff 2004; Olden and Rooney 2006) and progressive global warming (Leppäkoski et al. 2002; Rahel 2008; Penk et al. 2016). Non-native aquatic species are most often introduced into areas outside their native ranges through human-derived activities, such as ships' ballast water (Jude et al. 1992), aquaculture (Hill 2008), or indirectly through species' natural migration abilities (Šlapanský et al. 2017; Janáč et al. 2019) facilitated by man-made ecological corridors as initial expansion pathways (Bij de Vaate et al. 2002). Once established in new areas, they often have particularly pronounced impacts on native communities and overall ecosystem functioning (Strayer 2010; Simberloff et al. 2013; Pyšek et al. 2020; Ricciardi et al. 2021).

The round goby *Neogobius melanostomus* (Pallas, 1814), which originates from the Ponto-Caspian region and is one of the most notorious examples of an invasive aquatic species, has been the object of much laboratory and field research in recent decades (Cerwenka et al. 2023). Since it was first recorded outside its native range in 1990 in the Gulf of Gdansk (Skóra and Stolarski 1993), this fish has quickly established highly abundant populations (Corkum et al. 2004; Johnson et al. 2005) in areas stretching from the Great Lakes of North America (Jude et al. 1992, Ricciardi and MacIsaac 2000) to numerous Central and Western European rivers (Jurajda et al. 2005; Manné et al. 2013; Roche et al. 2015) and localities around the Baltic Sea (Azour et al. 2015; Quattrocchi et al. 2023). This species possesses many traits that allow it to successfully colonise novel ecosystems (Corkum et al. 2004; Kornis et al. 2012), including, above all, early sexual maturation coupled with short life cycles and small individual adult size (Simonović et al. 2001; Gutowsky and Fox 2012; Masson et al. 2018); a highly effective reproductive strategy (including portioned spawning several times a year) (Kulikova and Fandeeva 1975; Stammler and Corkum 2005); parental care (Sapota 2004; Vivó-Pons et al. 2023); high tolerance towards abiotic factors such as temperature and salinity (Behrens et al. 2017; Christensen et al. 2021); and aggressive behaviour (L'avrinčíková and Kováč 2007; Vivó-Pons et al. 2023). Adding to these, the successful establishment and spread of round goby depend on the ability to exploit food resources in the newly invaded ecosystem, as generally observed in the non-native species, which is usually achieved via opportunistic feeding strategies and the capacity to adapt rapidly (Diggins et al. 2002; Carman et al. 2006; Copp et al. 2008). The introduction of the invasive round goby into a new ecosystem can have a significant impact on food web dynamics, mainly through direct predation on macroinvertebrate communities (Kornis et al. 2012; Barton et al. 2005; Krakowiak and Pennuto 2008; Mikl et al. 2017; van Deurs et al. 2021). Generally, as an invasion progresses, the early stages are characterised by low population densities and abundant potential food sources, which allow invaders to extensively exploit a wide range of resources (Iacarella et al. 2015). This leads to high feeding rates and the rapid expansion of the invading population, as observed in studies by Phillips (2009), Raby et al. (2010) and Burton et al. (2010). By contrast, resource availability is more restricted in mature and established populations with higher conspecific densities where there is greater intraspecific competition (Brownscombe and Fox 2012; Azour et al. 2015).

Most of the numerous studies focussing on characterising the round goby's predatory activity (summarised by Marsden et al. 1996; Kornis et al. 2012; Števo and Kováč 2016; Dashinov and Uzunova 2020) have relied on descriptive approaches (via gut content analysis) and only provide limited information on, for example, niche and food preferences in specific localities (Amundsen et al. 1996). While some studies have emphasised the importance of certain taxa in the diet of round gobies (Polačik et al. 2009; Kirilenko and Shemonaev 2012) and the threat this species can pose to macroinvertebrates assemblages (Kuhns and Berg 1999; Barton et al. 2005; Míkl et al. 2017; van Deurs et al. 2021), such methods may overestimate prey significance by not accounting for food digestion rates and dynamics. This approach captures only a snapshot of prey present at a given time, which potentially distorts total consumption estimations since the relative abundance of prey items in the digestive tract may not reflect the proportion of actually consumed prey (Lagroe and Bollache 2006).

Several methods can be employed to quantify prey consumption and thus the predatory impact of a species (Elliot and Persson 1978; Durbin et al. 1983), including indirect methods based on bioenergetic models (Karjalainen et al. 1997; Hartman and Hayward 2007) and a direct method that estimates the predator's daily food intake *in situ* (Sun et al. 2016). The *in situ* approach is based on measuring stomach or gut fullness, which indicates the quantity of prey consumed. It is corrected by the evacuation rate (R) that quantifies the mass of food expelled from the digestive tract per unit of time (Talbot 1985; Bromley 1994). This correction is necessary because R primarily regulates feeding rates (Hedden et al. 2020). While both methods have limitations, *in situ* estimations appear more accurate (Bajkov 1935; Elliott and Persson 1978; Kawaguchi et al. 2007; Richter et al. 2018). This approach can be used under field conditions (Worischka and Mehner 1998; Rindorf 2004) and is based on fewer assumptions (Bartell et al. 1986), which improves its reliability. Hence, knowledge about the evacuation rate can be essential for the correct evaluation of the importance of particular food items found in the fish by preventing the underestimation of easily digestible foods and the overestimation of foods that are more difficult to digest (MacNeil et al. 2001; Gerking 1994). This enables us to potentially estimate the direct impact of non-native fish species on food webs and their indirect influence on native fish through competition for food.

The evacuation rate can be affected by various factors including which part of the digestive tract is considered, i.e. the stomach, foregut or the entire tract (Bromley 1994; Grove and Crawford 1980). However, temperature and predator size are considered to be the most important factors (Noble 1973; Garber 1983; Mills et al. 1984; Temming and Andersen 1992; Temming et al. 2002). Multiple studies have confirmed that there are significant variations in evacuation rates difficult to digest between prey species (Jones 1974; Macdonald et al. 1982), primarily due to their body structures (Singh-Renton 1990; dos Santos and Jobling 1992; Andersen 1999) since, in general, hard-bodied prey tends to be expelled much more slowly than soft-bodied items (Jones 1974). Given that an inverse dependency has also been observed (Hölker and Temming 1996), an analysis of the integument structure of the prey (Macdonald et al. 1982; Couturier et al. 2013), as well as its nutritional value and content (Bromley 1994; Zhu et al. 2015; Bonvini et al. 2018), should also be undertaken.

In terms of feeding strategies, previous experimental studies have primarily focused on quantifying the evacuation rate after single-food treatments (Pääkkönen and Marjomäki 1997; Bromley 1987). However, Tekinay et al. (2003) highlight certain limitations associated with this approach, largely because it does not replicate the natural feeding rhythms and evacuation patterns usually observed in nature, especially in omnivorous species (Hofer et al. 1982; Bromley 1994). Notably, the application of multiple meals (continuous feeding) has been reported

to induce a significantly higher evacuation rate (García-Ortega et al. 2010) in comparison to fish fed only once (Bromley 1988). Considering the pivotal role of both food resource availability and species-specific traits in determining the success of biological invasion processes (Phillips 2009; Brownscombe and Fox 2012; Vivó-Pons et al. 2023), we opted to compare these two feeding regimes in this study.

Comprehensive data on the consumption rates of individual prey species (including the gut evacuation rate) providing accurate evaluations of the predation pressure exercised by the highly invasive round goby are still lacking. Therefore, while considering how the round goby's diet changes in terms of ontogeny, season, daytime and environmental conditions, which can lead to shifts in food resource dynamics and availability (Walsh et al. 2007; Pennuto et al. 2010; Borcherding et al. 2013; Bhagat et al. 2015; Števo ve and Kováč 2016; Olson and Janssen 2017), we aimed to estimate and test gut evacuation rates in the round goby in terms of different prey types and under variable food availability scenarios (continuous feeding vs. non-continuous feeding), and diverse thermal conditions.

Based on the previous findings outlined above, we hypothesized that gut evacuation rates would differ depending on the type of prey (hard-bodied vs. soft-bodied prey), temperature conditions, and prey availability. We predicted that the round goby would exhibit faster food evacuation rates when fed continuously, evacuate soft-bodied prey more rapidly than hard-bodied ones, and have faster evacuation rates at higher temperatures.

Materials and methods

Collection and maintenance of study species

The round gobies were collected in late May and at the end of August 2019 using electrofishing (a backpack-pulsed-DC electrofishing unit ELT60II GI HONDA GXV 50; Hans Grassl GmbH, Germany) in the river Elbe near Dolní Žleb (North Bohemia, Czech Republic GPS: 50°50'39.9"N, 14°13'01.5"E) from a recently established population (Buiřič et al. 2015). Specimens representing the most common size cohort at the invaded locality (total length, TL = 55–75 mm) were transported to the experimental facilities of the Institute of Aquaculture and Protection of Waters FFPW USB in České Budějovice and acclimated in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS, total volume of 1600 l) for at least one week prior to the experiments. Physical-chemical water parameters such as, temperature (20.22 ± 0.07 and 14.19 ± 0.04 °C), oxygen saturation (94.05 ± 0.25 and $92.05 \pm 0.33\%$) and pH (7.67 ± 0.02 and 7.68 ± 0.02), were controlled on a daily basis using an HQ40d digital multimeter (Hach Lange GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany). The experimental temperature was gradually adjusted by approximately 1 °C every four days during the initial acclimatization period.

In accordance with our observations of the invaded localities along the river Elbe, as well as findings from other river systems (Ghedotti et al. 1995; Ray and Corkum 1997; French and Jude 2001; Diggins et al. 2002; Barton et al. 2005), three different types of prey (molluscs, amphipods and insect larvae) were chosen to represent the predominant macrozoobenthic groups in the round goby's diet (e.g. Phillips et al. 2003; Borza et al. 2009; Števo ve and Kováč 2016; Všeticková et al. 2018). Specifically, the killer shrimp *Dikerogammarus villosus* (Sowinsky, 1894), pill clam (*Pisidium* sp.) and chironomid larvae (*Chironomus* sp.) were used. Specimens of *D. villosus* were collected at the same localities as the round gobies were captured. *Pisidium* sp. were sampled in a tributary pond (Točník, South Bohemia, Czech Republic GPS: 48°56'57.8"N, 14°55'39.3"E), while live chironomid larvae were purchased from a pet store.

Experimental design

Based on the modified methodology proposed by Richter et al. (2018), we performed a series of six experimental trials to test gut evacuation rates in round gobies under different prey availabilities (two different feeding modes), prey types (three different prey items) and seasons. The latter were represented by two temperatures corresponding to the common/actual thermal conditions of the water at invaded localities on the river Elbe (taken from long-term data gathered during field surveys) in summer ($T = 20 \pm 0.035$ °C; mean \pm SE; season A; series of experiments 1–3 performed in July 2019) and spring/autumn ($T = 14 \pm 0.027$ °C; mean \pm SE; season B; series of experiments 4–6 performed in October 2019). Prey availability was varied by providing (i) food only at the beginning of the experiment (non-continual feeding) or (ii) continuously throughout the experiment (continual feeding).

Fish were starved for 48 h prior to each experimental trial to ensure the complete emptying of their alimentary tracts. To avoid possible cannibalism provoked by starvation and to ensure that a particular individual consumed a given amount of food, all fish were placed separately in experimental arenas (plastic boxes, each with a total volume of 2.4 l and water volume of 2.2 l) equipped with aeration and shelter. All experimental arenas had opaque walls to prevent visual contact between tested fish or any other visual disturbance that might represent an additional stressor. The light regime was set to 14 h light (intensity of 1000 lux.m²): 10 h dark, corresponding to the light regime during the vegetation season in the field, with simulations of dusk and dawn. The water parameters (T , O_2 and conductivity) in each experimental arena were monitored daily.

After the 48-hour starvation period, the round goby were fed with the tested food (food A) consisting of one of three different types of prey depending on the trial number (Table 1a, Fig. 1). Each type of prey was provided in quantities corresponding to similar weights to standardise the initial mass between treatments, regardless of the prey species (Table 1b). Subsequently, two hours later, any remains of tested prey (food A) were removed from all experimental arenas, which signalled the start of the main experiment phase and sampling. Fish whose tested prey (food A) intake was not observed were excluded from the experiment. Then, experimental arenas were randomly marked with colour clips to distinguish between non-continuous and continuous feeding modes. Following this, half of the individuals were not fed with any additional prey (the non-continuous feeding mode) (Fig. 1a), while the other half of the fish were continuously fed with a different type of prey (food B) (Table 1a, Fig. 1b), which was easily distinguishable to ensure the correct identification of the tested type of prey (food A) during subsequent fish dissection. To maintain constant food availability and experimental arenas were checked every four hours (Fig. 1b).

In total, we tested 420 fish, of which 70 were sampled during each experimental trial (which included one tested prey type, one temperature and two feeding modes) over 36 h at seven time points: 0, 2, 5, 9, 16, 24 and 36 h after the start of the main part of the experiment trial. At each time point, five randomly chosen fish from each feeding mode (non-continuous and continuous) were sampled. The collected fish were killed by overdosing with an MS-222 anaesthetic solution before being immediately frozen in dry ice to inhibit all metabolic processes in the digestive system. Specimens were then stored in a deep freezer (-80 °C) until processing, which took place within maximum of two weeks.

Table 1. Description of tested food and mean wet weights of experimental prey species. a) Combinations of tested food (Food A) and easily distinguishable additional food (Food B) used in the experiment. b) The mean wet weights of the experimental food prey species used in estimating the interaction between prey type and the gastric evacuation rate of round goby and their corresponding numbers of provided prey individuals n .

a)		
Experiment no.	Food A (tested food)	Food B (additional food)
1,4	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>
2,5	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae
3,6	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.

b)		
Prey type	Wet weight [g (mean \pm S.D.)]	n
<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	0.0620 \pm 0.0085	12
<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	0.0746 \pm 0.0154	6
<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	0.0696 \pm 0.0153	4

Figure 1. Gut evacuation rate experimental design. (a) Non-continual feeding mode; (b) Continual feeding mode. Solid red arrows represent the application of tested food (Food A) and additional food (Food B); dashed lines indicate the removal of tested food (food A) remains. Blue arrows represent the checking times (every 4 hours) when additional food (Food B) was provided if necessary to ensure continuous feeding. Green arrows represent the sampling time points.

Sample processing

Before the gut determination of the round gobies was performed, measurements of total length (TL; mm), standard length (SL; mm) and body weight (W; g) were taken, and their sex determined (Kornis et al. 2012). Subsequently, fish were individually dissected. The gut extraction was conducted following Manko (2016). The removed complete gut (together with the food content) was weighed (EX224M analytical balance, Ohaus Corporation, USA), its length measured, and the position of each food type (food A and B) observed. Then, the gut content (foods A and B separately) was carefully placed on previously heated (30 minutes at 500 °C in a muffle furnace) and weighed glass-microfibre discs (grade MGF, diameter 50 mm, Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany) to determine its wet weight (WW) with an analytical microbalance (M3P, Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany). Finally, samples of the gut content (food A and B), the fish carcasses and the empty dissected gut were dried at 105 °C overnight and stored in a desiccator to determine their dry weight (DW) with a microbalance.

Statistical analyses

The evacuation rate (R), represented by the regression coefficient, was determined through statistical modelling of the relative gut content weight over time. The relative gut content (GI) was defined as the proportion of the dry weight (DW) of the tested food (food A) remaining in the gut at a given time vs. the fish's dry body weight. The evacuation rate, expressed as the proportion lost from the gut per hour, can be described by several models, the most frequently used of which are linear and exponential functions (Elliott and Persson 1978; Bromley 1994). We found that the exponential function was the most suitable for our data as it had the fewest residual variations. Specifically, we applied the model represented by

$$GI_t = GI_0 e^{-Rt}$$

where GI_t is the relative gut content at time t , GI_0 is initial intestine content at time t_0 after feeding (h), and R is the evacuation rate (Elliott and Persson 1978).

We fitted the equation using generalised linear models (GLMs) with a Gaussian distribution (the log link function applied) and tested the relationship between the relative gut content GI used as a response variable and explanatory variables: (I) 'Time' (continuous numerical variable), (II) 'Prey availability' (two-level factor), and (III) 'Prey type' (three-level factor) separately for each season (see below). The improvement of the fitted relationships by the addition of interaction terms – one- and two-order interactions between all given explanatory variables – was tested using likelihood ratio tests. In order to avoid errors with log-transforming observations of empty guts at specific times, all zero values of relative gut content were replaced by 0.871 mg to represent half of the overall minimum gut content mass. The use of a Gaussian distribution was appropriate given that the histogram of model residuals was found to be close to the Gaussian; the assumption of homoscedasticity was also fulfilled. The significances of all relationships were tested by partial F -tests.

The independence of the initial consumption of prey and size of fish – used as explanatory variables – during the experimental treatments was tested given that this issue may potentially affect the obtained conclusions. Using GLMs with the binomial distribution (logistic link function applied), the consumption probability was detected as significantly greater when round gobies were fed with chironomids

than when fed with either *Dikerogammarus villosus* or *Pisidium* sp. (Suppl. material 1; $p < 0.05$). Therefore, individual values of *GI* were weighted by the proportions between prey consumed by the round goby and the total amount of offered prey, i.e. a weighted GLM was used to fit a shift in *GI*. In addition, significantly different consumption probabilities and significant differences in *SL* (tested using GLM with gamma distribution with the log link function applied) were also detected between the two seasons (Suppl. material 3; $p < 0.05$). Thus, two separate models with *GI* as a response were fitted for each 'season' to yield the regression coefficients representing the evacuation rate. Nevertheless, the fitted round goby *SL* in season B was only 2.06 mm higher than in season A, whilst *SL* variance was very low and similar in both seasons (Suppl. material 2). Based on these findings and given that it was the focus of our study, the factor 'season' (which represents different temperatures and temporarily distinct round goby stocks) was also left as the explanatory variable in a single *GI* model to test the significance of its additive effect. No other significant differences in the consumption probability or *SL* range for any explanatory variables of the interactions were detected ($p > 0.05$; sporadically marginal interactions detected). All data analyses and graphical procedures were performed using R software (CRAN, version 4.1.1).

Results

A total of 420 round gobies (TL: 53–80 mm; mean \pm SD = 67.7 \pm 5.53 mm) were tested in a series of six experiments.

Seasonal variation represented by two different thermal conditions (14 and 20 °C) had a significant additive effect on changes in the relative gut content ($p < 0.001$, Table 2, Suppl. material 2). Specifically, in Season A (20 °C), a 12.4% decrease in *GI* was observed compared to Season B (14 °C), based on the respective regression coefficients.

Season A: 20 °C

The second-order interaction of 'Time \times Prey availability \times Prey type' in modelling effects on the relative gut content (*GI*) was significant ($p < 0.01$, Table 3) and both 'Prey type' and 'Time' had significant effects on the relative gut content itself (Table 3).

Table 2. Relationships between relative gut content (*GI*) and explanatory variables, i.e. prey availability, prey type, season and time. Weighted generalised linear models (GLM) with Gaussian distribution (with the log link function applied) were used to fit and test the relationships. The significances of all relationships were tested using partial *F*-tests. Asterisks following *p*-values denote significance. Model $R^2 = 0.77$. *df* = degrees of freedom.

<i>GI</i> - Prey availability \times Prey \times Time + Season					
Variable	<i>df</i>	Deviance	<i>F</i> value	<i>p</i> -value	
Prey availability	1	0.0074	0.03	0.865	
Prey	2	0.0078	13.47	<0.001	***
Time	1	0.0090	90.06	<0.001	***
Season	1	0.0077	18.90	<0.001	***
Prey availability \times Prey	2	0.0075	3.36	0.036	*
Prey availability \times Time	1	0.0101	153.42	<0.001	***
Prey \times Time	2	0.0074	1.07	0.344	
Prey availability \times Prey \times Time	2	0.0079	15.19	<0.001	***
Residual deviance: 0.0074 on 407 residual <i>df</i>					

Table 3. Relationship between relative gut content (*GI*) and prey availability, prey type and time evaluated for both seasons (seasons A and B) separately. Generalised linear models (GLMs) with Gaussian distribution (with the log link function applied) were used to fit and test the relationships. Season A: $R^2 = 0.75$; Season B: $R^2 = 0.82$, $df =$ degrees of freedom. The significances of all relationships were tested using partial *F*-tests. Asterisks following approximal *p*-values represent different significance levels: * 0.05, ** 0.01, *** 0.001.

Model: <i>GI</i> - Prey availability × Prey × Time					
Season A					
Variable	<i>df</i>	Deviance	<i>F</i> value	<i>p</i> -value	
Prey availability	1	0.0036	3.00	0.085	.
Prey	2	0.0037	3.92	0.022	*
Time	1	0.0040	24.13	<0.001	**
Prey availability × Prey	2	0.0036	0.39	0.665	.
Prey availability × Time	1	0.0046	58.39	<0.001	***
Prey × Time	2	0.0037	2.58	0.078	.
Prey availability × Prey × Time	2	0.0038	5.33	0.006	**
Residual deviance: 0.0036 on 198 residual <i>df</i>					
Season B					
Prey availability	1	0.0032	2.46	0.118	.
Prey	2	0.0039	22.50	<0.001	***
Time	1	0.0043	70.84	<0.001	***
Prey availability × Prey	2	0.0034	6.71	0.002	**
Prey availability × Time	1	0.0049	103.82	<0.001	***
Prey × Time	2	0.0033	2.76	0.066	.
Prey availability × Prey × Time	2	0.0036	11.35	<0.001	***
Residual deviance: 0.0032 on 198 residual <i>df</i>					

The analyses revealed that in continual feeding mode, the highest evacuation rate was for the *Pisidium* sp. ($R = 0.2694 \pm 0.044$ g·g⁻¹ fish·h⁻¹; mean i.e. grams of prey per gram of fish per hour \pm SE; further h⁻¹; Table 4a) as complete food depletion took place 16 h after food intake (Fig. 2a), while chironomid larvae were completely evacuated within 24 hours, representing the second highest value in terms of evacuation rate ($R = 0.2043 \pm 0.029$ h⁻¹). *Dikerogammarus villosus* had the lowest evacuation rate of all prey types ($R = 0.1330 \pm 0.013$ h⁻¹), with total food depletion taking place only after 36 hours (Fig. 2a). Conversely, the lowest evacuation rate in non-continual feeding mode was observed for *Pisidium* sp. ($R = 0.02407 \pm 0.002$ h⁻¹; Table 4a) and the fastest for *Dikerogammarus villosus* ($R = 0.04516 \pm 0.005$ h⁻¹; Table 4a), the latter represented by the lowest relative gut content 36 h after food intake. None of the tested 'Prey types' were completely digested within 36 h in the non-continual feeding mode (Fig. 2a).

Season B: 14 °C

The second-order interaction of 'Time × Prey availability × Prey type' in modelling effects on the relative gut content was significant ($p < 0.001$, Table 3) and the effect of 'Prey type' on the relative gut content was also significant ($p < 0.001$).

The evacuation rates in the continual feeding mode varied between ($R = 0.1091 \pm 0.009$ h⁻¹) for *Dikerogammarus villosus* and the highest evacuation rate ($R = 0.2746 \pm 0.032$ h⁻¹) for *Pisidium* sp. (Table 4b), which significantly differed from the evacuation rate of chironomid larvae under the same feeding mode (Fig. 3b). The round gobies tested in continual feeding mode evacuated all the experimental food within 36 h (*D. villosus*), with complete gut evacuation after 24 h for chironomid larvae and after 16 h for *Pisidium* sp. (Fig. 2b). The lowest evacuation rate in the non-continual feeding mode was observed for chironomid larvae ($R = 0.01408 \pm 0.002$ h⁻¹) and the highest evacuation

Figure 2. Change in the relative gut content (GI) over time in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) in two different seasons (season A represented by $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and season B represented by $T = 14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) fed with three different prey species: 1. *Pisidium* sp. (red); 2. *Chironomus* sp. larvae (green); 3. *Dikerogammarus villosus* (blue), and in two different feeding modes: 1. Non-con = non-continual feeding mode (shown by dashed lines) and 2. Con = continual feeding mode (shown by solid lines). Relative gut content expressed as a ratio of the dry weight (DW) of the tested food (food A) for each treatment at the time of sampling vs. fish dry body weight [$\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$]. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals around mean estimates.

rate for *Pisidium* sp. ($R = 0.02676 \pm 0.002\text{ h}^{-1}$) (Table 4b). None of the tested 'Prey types' were completely digested within 36 h in non-continual feeding mode (Fig. 2b).

Prey type-specific differences between seasons

We observed prey-type-specific differences in evacuation rates between seasons. For *Dikerogammarus villosus*, the highest evacuation rate was observed in season A ($20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for both continual and non-continual prey availability (Fig. 2, Table 4). Conversely, all individuals fed with *Pisidium* sp. had faster evacuation rates in season B ($14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in both feeding modes (Table 4). Overall, the fastest evacuation rate for the *Chironomus* sp. larvae was observed in the continual prey availability at the lower temperature, i.e. in season B ($14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) (Table 4). For the non-continual feeding mode, the evacuation rate of chironomid larvae observed in season A ($20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) ($R = 0.02873 \pm 0.003\text{ h}^{-1}$) was faster than for the lower temperature conditions (Table 4).

Gut evacuation as a function of the food availability

According to the 95% confidence intervals, there was no observed overlap between the two feeding modes in the mean values of the evacuation rates in each season (Fig. 3), which indicates that there were significant differences between them. All prey types were digested and evacuated significantly faster in round gobies fed continuously (Table 4). By contrast, in the non-continual feeding mode, no round goby had completely evacuated its gut content 36 hours after feeding, unlike the continuously fed fish (Fig. 2).

Figure 3. Overlap between the 95% confidence intervals of the gastric evacuation rates (R ; $n = 420$) for all experimental treatments (three different prey types and two feeding modes) in both experimental seasons ($T = 14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $T = 20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*).

Table 4. Gastric evacuation rates R [h^{-1}] in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) under different treatments. Each experimental treatment combined different season (water temperature), prey type and feeding mode. A, Season A (temperature 20 °C). B, Season B (temperature 14 °C). Evacuation rates (mean \pm SE) are given as absolute values, while values in parentheses represent real R values. Prey types: pill clam (*Pisidium* sp.), chironomid larvae (*Chironomus* sp.) and killer shrimp (*Dikerogammarus villosus*). For the gastric evacuation rate the 95% confidence interval (95% CI) is also presented.

a)					
Treatment			R [h^{-1}]	95% CI	
Season	Prey availability	Prey type	(mean \pm SE)	lower	upper
A	Non-continual	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	0.024 (-0.024) \pm 0.002	-0.028	-0.019
A	Non-continual	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	0.029 (-0.029) \pm 0.003	-0.034	-0.022
A	Non-continual	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	0.045 (-0.045) \pm 0.005	-0.054	-0.035
A	Continual	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	0.269 (-0.269) \pm 0.044	-0.346	-0.173
A	Continual	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	0.204 (-0.204) \pm 0.029	-0.252	-0.140
A	Continual	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	0.133 (-0.133) \pm 0.013	-0.156	-0.104
b)					
Treatment			R [h^{-1}]	95% CI	
Season	Prey availability	Prey type	(mean \pm SE)	lower	upper
B	Non-continual	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	0.027 (-0.027) \pm 0.002	-0.030	-0.023
B	Non-continual	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	0.014 (-0.014) \pm 0.002	-0.017	-0.011
B	Non-continual	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	0.018 (-0.018) \pm 0.002	-0.021	-0.014
B	Continual	<i>Pisidium</i> sp.	0.275 (-0.275) \pm 0.032	-0.329	-0.206
B	Continual	<i>Chironomus</i> sp. larvae	0.225 (-0.225) \pm 0.028	-0.272	-0.164
B	Continual	<i>Dikerogammarus villosus</i>	0.109 (-0.109) \pm 0.009	-0.127	-0.088

Discussion

Impact of food availability on round goby gut evacuation rates

Our study demonstrates differences in evacuation rates in the round goby, with the continual feeding mode resulting in the higher evacuation rates compared to the non-continual feeding mode. Multiple-food application during the continual feeding mode accelerated the process, causing fish to evacuate particular food types 5–10 times faster than those fed only once (Table 4). These observations are consistent

with previous studies (Noble 1973; Jones 1974; Elliott 1975; Persson 1981, 1982) demonstrating that the presence of additional food leads to higher evacuation rates (Tekinay et al. 2003). This can be seen by the steeper slope in Fig. 2, which indicates more rapid relative gut-content loss over time. This can be attributed to mechanical factors whereby the tested prey is pushed along the digestive tract by subsequently ingested food (Riche et al. 2004), possibly aided by the distribution of mucus-secreting goblet cells (Hur et al. 2016). However, the evacuation process is preceded by muscular and enzymatic activities (Nilsson and Brönmark 2000). Thus, one possible explanation for our findings could be intensified and accelerated metabolism involving greater enzymatic activity due to increased gut content (O'Connor et al. 2000), where the higher quantity of food, compared to fish fed only once, may affect digestive enzyme activity (Peres et al. 1998). Moreover, using two types of prey (Food A, Food B) can induce a potential synergistic metabolic response, where the digestion and metabolism of one prey type influence the processing of another, especially considering that different diet compositions (varied prey types) can selectively activate specific enzymes (German et al. 2004). Therefore, the biochemical composition appears to be a crucial factor (Caviedes-Vidal et al. 2000), affecting overall gut transition and digestion processes, which may be heightened in response to temporary increases in specific nutritional prey content (German et al. 2004). This effect is particularly significant for species known for their diverse diet, indicating modulation of overall digestive enzyme activities on a larger scale (Karasov 1992).

At the same time, differences in food digestion and evacuation rates according to food availability coincide with field observations since, in the early phases of invasions, individuals of a non-native species take advantage of low population densities and abundant food supply to exploit a wide range of accessible resources (Iacarella et al. 2015). This leads to higher feeding rates and rapid growth of the invading population (Phillips 2009; Burton et al. 2010; Raby et al. 2010). By contrast, in mature and established populations with higher conspecific densities resource availability is more restricted and leads to intensified intraspecific competition (Brownscombe and Fox 2012; Azour et al. 2015).

Prey type-specific differences in gut evacuation rates

We expected to observe differences between fish fed with different prey species since prey body structure influences evacuation rates (Jones 1974; Singh-Renton 1990; dos Santos and Jobling 1992; Andersen et al. 1999). In our study, round gobies exhibited the fastest evacuation rates when fed on *Pisidium* sp. in both seasons (under different thermal conditions) and when food was continuously available. Those observations contradict the pattern observed in the majority of the studies whereby soft-bodied prey is digested and evacuated faster than hard-bodied prey (Jones 1974; Singh-Renton and Bromley 1999; Temming and Herrmann 2003). Typically, an external protective body structure such as a shell or exoskeleton acts as a barrier for digestive juices and slows down the digestion process (Jones 1974; dos Santos and Jobling 1992; Bromley 1994). One of the possible explanations behind our observations is that hard-shelled food resembles 'high-fibre' food or roughage and thus is transported faster through the digestive tract (Hilton et al. 1983). Moreover, it is important to consider species' digestive capabilities, which depend on differences between fish species in morphological features and levels of organisation in the digestive tract structure, in which the primary concern is to ensure optimum use of dietary nutrients (Ray and Ringø 2014). Therefore, depending on diet preferences and feeding behaviour, particular species adapt (Olsen and Ringø 1997; Ringø et al. 2003), which enhances the efficiency of their food processing and thus determines digestive tract

structure (Jiao et al. 2023). The omnivorous round goby is functionally classified as a stomachless fish due to its relatively simple, straight tubular-segmented digestive tract (Geevarghese 1983; Barton 2007), in which morphological adaptations are closely correlated to ontogenetic changes in the morphology of its robust molariform teeth (Ghedotti et al. 1995; Andraso et al. 2011a). Given that bivalves are the primary prey in round goby diets in both their native range (Demchenko and Tkachenko 2017) and in invaded localities (Diggins et al. 2002; Adámek et al. 2007; Kornis et al. 2012; van Deurs et al. 2021; Behrens et al. 2022), these adaptations enable it to exploit hard-shelled resources and feed on molluscs by crushing (Angradi 2018). This allows digestive enzymes to access soft tissues (Aarnio and Bonsdorff 1997) and ensure rapid gut transit through a short digestive tract that maximises food processing efficiency (Horn and Messer 1992), as observed in other stomachless species. This trait, which involves the mechanical breakdown of food before it reaches the intestines and is recognized as compensation for the lack of a stomach (Fänge and Grove 1979), likely explains the observed faster evacuation rates of *Pisidium* sp. in our study. Based on our post-experimental gut content analysis, it was evident that all *Pisidium* sp. individuals were thoroughly minced and crushed by the round gobies and, in almost all cases, after 16 hours it was impossible to discern the prey structure. In our opinion, this foraging adjustment almost certainly contributes to much faster evacuation rates.

In addition to the observed faster evacuation rates of *Pisidium* sp., it is crucial to consider the predator-prey size relationship. Although round gobies feed on a range of mussel sizes, experimental data reveal a preference for smaller individuals, most probably due to their ease of swallowing and thinner shells (Schwartzbach et al. 2020). Particularly interesting is the observation that some hard-bodied prey items such as Dreissenidae under 6 mm in size (Andraso et al. 2011b) remain intact after passing through the round goby intestine or like *Pisidium* sp. (Mack and Andraso 2015; Andraso et al. 2017) even survive gut passage. However, our observations differed as we failed to detect any persistent intact forms despite the individuals used in our experiments being smaller than 6 mm. Nonetheless, it is important to bear these findings in mind as they suggest that the actual predatory efficiency of round gobies on molluscs is unclear and could be overestimated in some cases. A similar pattern has been observed in *Ancylus fluviatilis* Müller, 1774 in the river Elbe, which appears to be a preferred food resource for the round goby (Richter et al. 2022). In this case, shell remnants persist in the rear sections of the digestive tract for an extended period and form stacked structures. This can lead to overestimations when comprehensively examining the full contents of the entire gut.

By contrast, the round gobies fed on another hard-bodied prey – *Dikerogammarus villosus* – exhibited the slowest gut evacuation rates when continuously fed, which was accompanied by notable mechanical food processing in the sampled digestive tracts. The observed delay in the complete evacuation of crustacean prey (36 h) can be attributed to the resistance of the cuticular exoskeleton to enzymatic breakdown (Bromley 1991; Andersen 1999; Temming and Herrmann 2003), while the subsequent increase in evacuation duration time is correlated with rising ash content within the prey (Couturier et al. 2013). This finding concurs with studies conducted in other fish species that report slower evacuation of prey with structural support than of prey without (Singh-Renton and Bromley 1999; Temming and Herrmann 2003; Gillum et al. 2012). Furthermore, the observed decrease in the evacuation rate of amphipod prey in our studies may suggest greater use of consumed nutrients (Le et al. 2019) since previous research has revealed a reduction in the efficiency of digestion and absorption processes if the gut transit time is shorter (Garber 1983; Lee et al. 2000). Therefore, the prolonged gut evacuation rate coupled with evident food breakdown observed in our study

suggests that *Dikerogammarus villosus* – alongside chironomids – can also serve as a nutritionally valuable food source and prey item providing fatty acid (Sushchik et al. 2006; Maazouzi et al. 2007). These potentially superior nutritional benefits are also supported by studies demonstrating the strong preference of round gobies for amphipod prey, which results in faster growth rates and better overall body condition than in diets based on bivalves (Polačik et al. 2009). This preference may be attributable to prolonged satiety, in which a slower evacuation rate could be an adaptation used during the species' transport and active dispersal to new localities, as the digestive tract capacity of gobies and their temporary food storage function are diminished by their secondary loss of an anatomically distinct stomach (Barton 2007), and lack of intestinal bulb (Trzeciak et al. 2012)—a simple dilatation at the anterior part of the intestine—commonly recognized as a substitute for the stomach in agastric fish (Kapoor et al. 1976; Mokhtar et al. 2021).

In some areas, round goby feed almost exclusively on amphipods, which can constitute up to 70–80% of their diets (Brandner et al. 2013). This finding and our results together suggest that even when round gobies exhibit preferences and prey exclusively on amphipods (Diggins et al. 2002; Polačik et al. 2009; Emde et al. 2014), they may still exert less pressure on this prey group in terms of evacuated biomass quantity per unit of time than on other prey, e.g. the tested chironomid larvae. This implies potentially less predatory pressure on amphipods (even when they are present throughout all seasons in the benthic community) than on other groups of macrozoobenthic organisms whose availability is more seasonally limited (Zinchenko et al. 2017; Pander et al. 2022). However, our suppositions are only supported by our laboratory findings regarding evacuation rates. Since the round goby is recognised as an omnivorous species that feeds on the most readily available prey (Kornis et al. 2012; Nurkse et al. 2016), we believe that – rather than food preferences – local prey abundances together with evacuation rates primarily govern the potential predatory pressure exercised by this species. Hence, dietary analysis and macrozoobenthic availability in local populations will provide more accurate and comprehensive information regarding potential predatory pressure in any particular locality.

We cannot exclude that the differences in gastric evacuation rates between prey types (Food A) were affected also by using different types of second prey (Food B) as our methods included invariable pairs of prey combinations that may occur in nature and the round goby diet (Szydłowska et al. 2024). For example, studies on *N. melanostomus* (Trzeciak et al. 2012) and other gobiid species (Jaroszewska et al. 2008; Wołczuk et al. 2015) have confirmed the presence of an oesogaster with alveolar glands and functions for enzyme secretion and mucus production. These features serve as an effective functional replacement for the conventional stomach, enhancing digestion, particularly evident in the utilization of protein-rich food sources (Wołczuk et al. 2015). Based on this, chironomid larvae, known for their high protein content and used as a subsequent meal (Food B; De la Noüe and Choubert 1985; Nath et al. 2015), could potentially contribute to the rapid evacuation of *Pisidium* sp., as observed in continual feeding mode. However, when considering the analysis of results from the non-continuous feeding mode, which can be regarded as a 'baseline' where each prey type was tested separately, it appears that chironomid larvae were digested and evacuated at different rates depending on the season, while the evacuation rate for *Pisidium* sp. followed by Diptera larvae in continual feeding mode remained the highest regardless of these conditions. Thus, other indicators, such as the size of prey—for instance, even when meal portions are of the same mass, smaller prey are likely to be evacuated and metabolized faster (Nilsson and Brönmark 2000)—are also possibly affecting the evacuation rate of *Pisidium* sp. when tested as Food A. Following that, similar justifications for the

possible effects could be applied to the other prey combinations tested within our study, depending on the specific example. Thus, the limited findings highlight the necessity for further investigation involving additional prey species, such as Food B, consistent across all three prey types examined in our study. This would be essential for gaining more robust insights into potential field scenarios. Moreover, factors such as surface area to volume ratio (Andersen 1999), shape (Karlsen and Andersen 2012), and energy density might also play a significant role in explaining our results, and their potential effects should be investigated in separate studies.

Seasonal temperature effects on gut evacuation rate

According to the literature, temperature is probably one of the most studied environmental factors (Shrable et al. 1969; Brett and Higgs 1970; Persson 1979; Bascinar et al. 2016; Dürrani and Seyhan 2019; Horstman 2020) since it has a major effect on metabolism, biochemical reactions and digestion in fish, and so naturally affects evacuation rates (Pääkkönen and Marjomäki 1997; Gillum et al. 2012). We predicted faster evacuation rates at 20 °C than at 14 °C given that this rate is commonly observed to speed up as temperatures increase (He and Wurtsbaugh 1993; De et al. 2016; Mazumder et al. 2020). Indeed, based on comparisons of the yielded coefficients, our study suggests a potential effect of temperature on the round goby evacuation rate. However, contrary to our expectations, no consistent pattern emerged across different prey types between seasons, thereby indicating the effects of temperature as a prey-type dependent. Following that, results confirmed anticipated thermal dependency in round gobies fed on *Dikerogammarus villosus*, with faster evacuation rates observed at higher temperatures in both feeding modes. This agrees with the findings reported by Stehlik et al. (2015) for the clearnose skate *Rostroraja eglanteria* (Bosc, 1800), where similar ranges of evacuation rates, observed at almost the same temperatures as in our experiment, also reflect the typical thermal dependency (Wu et al. 2015; Horstman 2020). Conversely, round gobies fed on *Pisidium* sp. in both feeding modes exhibited faster evacuation at lower temperatures. This observation can possibly find its rationale in the significant seasonal differences in observed consumption probabilities (evident from the graphical representation of the initial relative gut content; Fig. 2). Specifically, round gobies tested in season B (14 °C; spring/autumn conditions) consumed more *Pisidium* sp. than those tested in season A (20 °C, summer conditions), as shown by the observed initial relative gut content. This matches field observations whereby larger round gobies in spring and autumn chiefly base their diet on molluscs (Borcherding et al. 2013). Since the round gobies tested in season B were also slightly bigger (2.06 mm on average) than those tested in season A and the predator and prey body size is regarded as an important variable affecting evacuation rates (Beamish 1972; Fänge and Grove 1979; Andersen 1984; Bromley 1994; dos Santos and Jobling 1995; Seyhan et al. 2020), we cannot completely exclude their possible impact on the effects observed. However, we believe that the detected difference in the size (SL) of the fish used in the two seasons – by a magnitude of just a few mm – although statistically significant, is biologically irrelevant and likely did not affect the actual result of our study in any way.

As the continual feeding mode reflects conditions observed in the wild by simulating different prey type combinations, we can expect similar outcomes in nature. Following that, the inconsistency observed in temperature-related patterns in the evacuation rate of each prey type might be explained not only by the higher relevance of other tested variables but also by the round goby's wide environmental tolerance, as previously documented by several studies (Charlebois et al.

2001; Christensen et al. 2021), which is reflected in its broad temperature range (Moskal'kova 1996). Laboratory research has further corroborated these findings and demonstrated metabolic adaptability and ability of the species to thrive under disparate conditions, including temperatures ranging from 2.3 to 5.3 °C (Walsh et al. 2007; Silva et al. 2019) and its active feeding year-round even at low temperatures under natural conditions (Dashinov and Uzunova 2020). However, it is important to remember that seasonal changes in the effectiveness of prey use and diet are not only temperature-dependent but are also affected by particular prey types and their seasonal dynamics within the macroinvertebrate assemblages and thus by variations in the availability of food resources (Didenko et al. 2017). Therefore, the outcomes of our analysis underscore the importance of considering the interaction between all the abovementioned and tested conditions.

Comparison of food processing efficiency between the round goby and local native species

Compared to local native species such as ruffe *Gymnocephalus cernua* (Linnaeus, 1758) in the estuary of the river Elbe (Hölker and Temming 1996) and the river St. Louis (Henson and Newman 2000), our study found that, under the same thermal conditions, the round goby evacuates chironomid larvae up to three times faster. While the abovementioned studies primarily focussed on gastric evacuation rates (which assess stomachs), our findings relate to the gut evacuation rate that encompasses the whole alimentary tract due to its different structure. This variance in digestive anatomy may affect the comparability between species of evacuation rates. Nevertheless, this disparity might still indicate the superior efficiency of the round goby in acquiring food and competing for resources, consistent with findings from the experimental studies conducted by Bergstrom and Mesinger (2009), as the evacuation rates were found to regulate food intake rates (Aas et al. 2013; Hedden et al. 2020). This efficiency, combined with its feeding plasticity and ability to feed on the most abundant local prey (Carman et al. 2006), could be linked to the observed depletion (Lauer et al. 2004; Rakauskas et al. 2013; Ramler and Keckeis 2019) – or even in some particular cases collapse – of indigenous fish populations (Jüza et al. 2018) and negative trends in macrozoobenthic assemblages (Pennuto et al. 2010; van Deurs et al. 2021).

On the other hand, research by Lagrue and Bollache (2006) into the persistence of gammarids in European bullhead *Cottus gobio* Linnaeus, 1758 stomachs over 24–30 hours at 14 °C suggests that the round goby may in fact be less efficient at food processing than other analogous native fish species that prey on amphipods. This implies a potential lack of superiority of a non-native predator over its native counterparts in competing for food resources in localities where they occur sympatrically (Janáč et al. 2018; Roje et al. 2021). Our study corroborates this observation given that, among all the offered prey types, the slowest evacuation rate while continuously feeding at the 14 °C exhibited by round gobies was for crustaceans. However, Lagrue and Bollache (2006) noted that the persistence time was strongly influenced by temperature and prey type (e.g. the invasive *Gammarus roeseli* Gervais, 1835 had significantly greater persistence at 14 °C than its native counterparts), which highlights potential variations in outcomes if *Dikerogammarus villosus* would be included given its more robust and thicker exoskeleton and resistance (Błońska et al. 2015). This raises questions regarding our previous statement, as the inclusion of *D. villosus* could influence the persistence time in native fish predators. However, it is important to emphasise that while the gut evacuation rate is a good predictor and plays a primary role in

regulating feeding rates (Hedden et al. 2020), the overall efficiency and impact of a predator depend on a series of factors including fish capture effectiveness and foraging behaviour (Gebauer et al. 2018; Franta et al. 2021), as well as the abundance of local prey populations.

Conclusions

Overall, our study shows that the round goby exhibits higher efficiency and effectiveness in food processing when feeding on chironomid and mollusc prey and, contrary to expectations, can maintain high evacuation rates even at low temperatures (when after feeding on bivalves). These findings suggest a potentially higher consumption rate and predatory pressure on the aforementioned types of prey, which are the main components of the round goby's diet (Phillips et al. 2003; Weimer 2003; Carman et al. 2006; Polačik et al. 2009; Kirilenko and Shemonaev 2012; Matern et al. 2021; van Deurs et al. 2021), as well as less impact on amphipod prey (Lederer et al. 2008). Moreover, our study confirmed the generally observed rule that the evacuation rate significantly increases in situations of greater prey availability. This indicates higher potential consumption efficiency under these conditions allowing to maximise yields from available resources, which could seriously affect native macrozoobenthic and fish assemblages (Barton et al. 2005; Rakauskas et al. 2013; Mikl et al. 2017) and potentially lead to decreased resource availability. We believe that further investigations focusing on modifying feeding scenarios and prey combinations should be prioritized to better understand food processing efficiency and, hence, possible predatory pressure on specific prey taxa.

Our research takes the first step toward accurately quantifying consumption and assessing the predatory impact of round gobies in colonized regions. By integrating laboratory-derived gut evacuation rates with field gut samples (Bernreuther et al. 2009), we can accurately calculate daily consumption (Elliot and Persson 1978). This, combined with data on macrozoobenthic assemblage densities, can offer comprehensive insights into predator-prey dynamics and consumption patterns in invasive species. Considering the environmental conditions used in the presented studies (primary food resource types, seasonal temperatures, and diverse prey availability scenarios), we believe our findings apply not only within local contexts but also to other colonized regions, where monitoring local populations can allow to assess predatory pressure and consumption rates estimations at both *per capita* and population levels. Following Stehlik et al. (2015), our findings will help quantify the consumption rate of round gobies in ecosystems, and we recommend that future research prioritizes the study of evacuation rates to improve estimates of prey use and predator efficiency.

Authors' Contribution:

S.W., L.R., B.D., P.F. research conceptualization; P.F., B.D., sample design and methodology; N.S., P.F. investigation and data collection; M.L., N.S. data analysis and interpretation; M.B. funding provision; N.S. writing - original draft; M.B., B.D., S.W., M.L., N.S. writing – review & editing.

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Ethics and Permits

All research pertaining to this article was carried out in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Czech Republic and obtained formal approval from the applicable ethics committee.

All animal handling was adhered to the legal requirements in the Czech Republic (§ 7 Law No. 114/1992 on The Protection of Nature and Landscape and § 6, 7, 9, and 10 Regulation No. 419/2012 on the Care, Breeding, and Use of Experimental Animals).

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Supplementary material 1

Consumption probability

Authors: Natalia Z. Szydłowska, Marek Let, Pavel Franta, Miloš Bujič, Susanne Worischka, Luise Richter, Bořek Drozd

Data type: pdf

Explanation note: Effect of prey type 1. Pis = *Pisidium* sp.; 2. Chiro = chironomid (*Chironomus* sp.) larvae; 3. Dikero = *Dikerogammarus villosus*, season (season A represents T = 20 °C and season B represents T = 14 °C) and prey availability: 1. Non-con = non-continual feeding mode; 2. Con = continual feeding mode; on the probability of being consumed by round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) individuals. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals around mean estimates (food consumption probability) within each tested factor level.

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Supplementary material 2

Change in the relative gut content (GI) in time in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) represented by different treatments

Authors: Natalia Z. Szydlowska, Marek Let, Pavel Franta, Miloš Buřič, Susanne Worischka, Luise Richter, Bořek Drozd

Data type: pdf

Explanation note: Season A represented by T = 20 °C (dot); Season B represented by T = 14 °C (triangle). Different prey species: 1. *Pisidium* sp. (red); 2. *Chironomus* sp. larvae (green); 3. *Dikerogammarus villosus* (blue). Feeding modes: 1. Non-con = non-continual feeding mode (shown by dashed lines) and 2. Con = continual feeding mode (shown by solid lines). Relative gut content expressed as a ratio of the dry weight (DW) of the tested food (food A) for each treatment at the time of sampling vs. fish dry body weight [g.g⁻¹].

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Supplementary material 3

Standard length (SL) differences in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) individuals used in experiments in the two seasons (A and B), with different prey type and prey availability

Authors: Natalia Z. Szydlowska, Marek Let, Pavel Franta, Miloš Buřič, Susanne Worischka, Luise Richter, Bořek Drozd

Data type: docx

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary material 2

Supplementary material 3

Table S1. Standard length (SL) differences in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) individuals used in experiments in the two seasons (A and B), with different prey type and prey availability.

Model: SL ~ Prey availability + Prey + Season + Time					
Variable	df	Deviance	F value	p-value	
Prey availability	1	2.9000	1.0530	0.3054	
Prey type	2	2.8954	0.2028	0.8166	
Time	6	2.9419	1.1642	0.3245	
Season	1	3.0301	19.4596	<0.001	***

CHAPTER 3

RISK PERCEPTION: CHEMICAL STIMULI IN PREDATOR DETECTION AND FEEDING BEHAVIOUR OF THE INVASIVE ROUND GOBY *NEOGOBIUS MELANOSTOMUS*

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My share on this work was about 50%.

Article

Risk Perception: Chemical Stimuli in Predator Detection and Feeding Behaviour of the Invasive Round Goby *Neogobius melanostomus*

Natalia Z. Szydlowska *, Pavel Franta

South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Zátěží 728/II, 389 25 Vodňany, Czech Republic; pfranta@frov.jcu.cz (P.F.); mlet@frov.jcu.cz (M.L.); vmiksovska@frov.jcu.cz (V.M.); buric@frov.jcu.cz (M.B.); drozd@frov.jcu.cz (B.D.)

* Correspondence: nszydlowska@frov.jcu.cz

Simple Summary: The round goby is considered one of the most widespread Ponto-Caspian invasive species, which poses a threat to ecosystems and food web alterations. While it is known for direct predation, its interactions with native higher predators and its feeding behaviour upon their presence remain unclear. Therefore, we investigated how the exposure to chemical alarm cues emitted by conspecifics and the odour of a native predator, the European eel, affects the round goby's feeding activity. Surprisingly, the gobies did not exhibit any pronounced threat sensitivity to both types of chemical stimuli, which was observed in unchanged food consumption probability and gut evacuation rates. The obtained outcomes suggest boldness, great efficiency in food processing, and a potential competitive advantage over native counterparts when colonising new ecosystems, irrespective of local higher predator presence.

Abstract: The round goby *Neogobius melanostomus* is a notoriously invasive fish originating from the Ponto-Caspian region that in recent decades has successfully spread across the globe. One of its primary impacts is direct predation; in addition, when entering new ecosystems, the round goby is likely to become a food resource for many higher native predators. However, little is known either about the indirect effects of predators on the round goby as prey or its feeding behaviour and activity. The non-consumptive effect of the presence of higher native predators presumably plays an important role in mitigating the impact of non-native round gobies as mesopredators on benthic invertebrate communities, especially when both higher- and mesopredators occupy the same habitat. We tested the food consumption probability and gut evacuation rates in round gobies in response to chemical signals from a higher predator, the European eel *Anguilla anguilla*. Gobies were placed individually in experimental arenas equipped with shelters and exposed to water from a tank in which (a) the higher predator had actively preyed on a heterospecific prey, earthworms *Lumbricus* sp. (the heterospecific treatment; HS); (b) the higher predator had fed on round gobies (the conspecific treatment; CS); or (c) the water was provided as a control treatment (C). To ensure exposure to the chemical stimuli, this study incorporated the application of skin extracts containing damaged-released alarm cues from the CS treatment; distilled water was used for the remaining treatments. No significant differences were observed in either the food consumption probability or gut evacuation rate in the tested treatments. Despite the lack of reaction to the chemical stimuli, round gobies did exhibit high evacuation rates ($R = 0.2323 \pm 0.011 \text{ h}^{-1}$; mean \pm SE) in which complete gut clearance occurred within 16 h regardless of the applied treatment. This rapid food processing suggests high efficiency and great pressure on resources regardless of the presence or not of a higher predator. These findings hint at the boldness of round gobies, which did not exhibit any pronounced threat sensitivity. This would seem to suggest great efficiency in food processing and a potential competitive advantage over local native species when colonising new ecosystems, irrespective of the presence of native predators. Our study did not detect any non-consumptive effect attributable to the higher predator, given that the feeding activity of the invasive round goby was not altered.

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Keywords: alarm cues; *shreckstoff*; food consumption; gut evacuation rate; predation efficiency; aquatic invasions; non-native species

1. Introduction

Alien invasive species continue to pose a significant threat to biodiversity [1]. Their rising impacts may be attributable in many cases to globalisation [2,3] and progressive global climate changes [4,5] and have serious ecological and economic consequences [6–8]. In recent decades, the Ponto-Caspian region has emerged as a notable source of fresh species introductions throughout Europe [9], which include a significant number of representatives from the Gobiidae (Actinopterygii) family [10]. At least five species have established populations in European inland freshwater ecosystems [11], of which the most widespread and well-known is the round goby *Neogobius melanostomus* (Pallas, 1814). This fish has successfully expanded its range worldwide [12] and now serves as a model species for studying invasions in freshwater ecosystems [13].

As an invasive species, the round goby exhibits numerous specific traits that have facilitated its successful colonisation of new freshwater and marine ecosystems on both sides of the Atlantic Ocean [14–17]. Key among the characteristics facilitating its establishment is its opportunistic feeding strategy [18,19] that guarantees effective food resource exploitation. However, since many introduced species are not only predators but also prey for native species when they enter new ecosystems, the round goby's ability to manage risks posed by unfamiliar predators might also be contributing to its invasive success [20,21].

When entering new ecosystems, the round goby notably disrupts community dynamics and food webs [22], primarily through direct predation on benthic invertebrate communities [23,24], as well as on fish fry and eggs [25,26]. Hence, depending on the round goby's diet shifts during ontogeny [27], as well as seasonal and/or environmental conditions [28–30], different macroinvertebrate assemblages will experience intense predatory pressure leading to significant declines [31–33]. Additionally, intensified foraging on particular taxa and competition for habitat and food resources will further contribute to the depletion of native fish abundance and richness [34–36], thereby leading potentially to their replacement [37]. Moreover, besides its commonly attributed role as a predator, the round goby has become an essential dietary item for numerous native higher-predator fish species [38–40] and in some cases is even the main food item due to its long-term presence in the ecosystem [41].

These predator–prey interactions are crucial drivers of trophic dynamics and structural and functional changes within ecosystems [42]. Recent studies have shown that predators can exert threats and affect prey populations not solely via direct consumption but also indirectly [43,44]. Non-consumptive effects are observed when mesopredators face the trade-off between predation risk and other activities such as, for instance, resource acquisition [45]. Compared to the direct foraging effect, non-consumptive effects appear to be equally or even more significant [46], since they can affect the entire prey population by inducing adaptations of defensive strategies [47]. This can lead to modifications in fish morphology, physiology, and behaviour where, depending on the length of exposure to the risk (acute or chronic), the response of fish will differ [48].

Following that, the early detection of a local predation risk presence represents a keystone ability for prey survival [49,50]. Foragers gather information by perceiving and relying on a variety of stimuli [44,51], with chemical communication believed to be fundamental for risk assessment and prey avoidance [52–55] irrespective of environmental conditions [56]. These stimuli include stress-inducing cues resulting from prey–predator interactions [57]. Both predator and prey specimens can actively release these cues: predator-borne cues include kairomones and digestion-released (dietary) cues recognisable by conspecifics of the consumed prey [58,59], while prey-borne cues derived from epidermic injuries or active foraging serve as pre-attack alarm alerts that warn conspecifics of the threat of a

potential attack [53,60–62]. As a result, all signals may lead to both behavioural [63–65] and physiological [59,66,67] anti-predatory responses, which are often specific to a given species [60,67]. Different fish species appear to respond differently to identical chemical pictures [68] or to the type of chemical signal to which they are exposed [69]. All of the abovementioned comprise adaptations that significantly contribute to increasing the prey survival rate [70].

Although significant advances have been made in studying predation on the round goby [71], our understanding of the indirect effects of the presence of higher predators on mesopredators (i.e., the round goby) remains limited. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to investigate whether or not round gobies respond to chemical stimuli and whether or not the presence of the local higher predator, the European eel *Anguilla anguilla* (Linnaeus, 1758), affects gobies' feeding and digestion efficiency. We assessed this by counting the number of prey items consumed and by analysing evacuation rates (R), i.e., the mass of food expelled from the digestive tract per unit of time [72]. This evacuation rate parameter is commonly used in direct in situ methods to quantify food consumption, e.g., [73–75], since it regulates feeding rates [76].

Foragers have to confront trade-offs between predator avoidance and other fitness-related activities [61,77]. This can manifest itself in altered feeding behaviour [78] including shifts in feeding-hiding ratios [63,79], a reduction in food intake in fish exposed to the chemical cues provided by higher predators [80–84], or even complete feeding latency [65,69,85]. Thus, we expected to observe similar reactions in round gobies. In addition to recognising predator odours, we predicted that the round goby would respond sharply to alarm cues derived from conspecific individuals. Therefore, we hypothesised that exposure to chemical cues, i.e., predator odour and conspecific alarm cues, would significantly contribute to a specific anti-predatory response. This response was expected to manifest itself in the form of decreased foraging activity and slower gut evacuation rates due potentially to lower consumption rates [86].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Collection and Maintenance of Study Organisms

N. melanostomus (a non-native mesopredator) individuals in a size range 55–75 mm were collected in the river Elbe (Dolní Žleb, North Bohemia, Czech Republic GPS: 50.50335 N, 14.13019 E) by electrofishing (a backpack pulsed-DC electrofishing unit FEG 1500, EFKO, Leutkirch, Germany) (~0.5 m water depth; 0.02–0.49 m s⁻¹ water velocity). Fish capture was conducted in a recently established population first documented by Buřič et al. [87]. Fish were transported to the experimental facilities of the Institute of Aquaculture and Protection of Waters (FFPW USB) in České Budějovice where they were acclimatised in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) with a total volume of 1600 L for at least one month before the experiments were conducted. Selected physical–chemical parameters (T, O₂, pH) were monitored using daily measurements conducted with an HQ40d digital multimeter (Hach Lange GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany).

A. anguilla (a native higher predator) were captured at another locality on the river Elbe (Lovosice, North Bohemia, Czech Republic; 50.5165686N, 14.0595781E), where the co-occurrence of these two species—as well as eel predation on round gobies—has been confirmed (obs. pers.). Given the shared habitat [88] and the similar temperature conditions required for growth and consumption [89–91], the European eel was chosen as the higher predator for our experiment. Eels sized 540–840 mm (known to feed on small-size fish species including round gobies; [92,93]) were transported to the facility and stocked in the two separate recirculating systems (RAS; 2 × 1600 L) and were subsequently used in the experiment. For at least one month before the experiment began, the eels were fed on round gobies (first group, representing the conspecific treatment; CS) or on common earthworms *Lumbricus terrestris* (Linnaeus, 1758) (second group, representing the heterospecific treatment; HS) to acclimatise them to the food to be used during the experiment and to

ensure adequate prey intake. All the abovementioned physical–chemical parameters were controlled daily.

The experimental food provided for the round gobies included *Chironomus* sp. larvae (frequently observed in their diet, [94,95]) purchased from a pet store and *Gammarus fossarum* (Koch in Panzer, 1835), selected as an alternative dietary source that is easily distinguishable from the tested food even after digestion. The *Gammarus fossarum* individuals (successfully preyed upon by round goby, [96]) were collected from Dobrovodský potok (Třebotovice, South Bohemia, Czech Republic; 48.9507 N, 14.5676 E), frozen on-site using dry ice, and subsequently stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until the beginning of the experiment.

2.2. Preparation of the Alarm Cues

The preparation of the alarm cues used in this study followed the methods described by Wisenden et al. [61]. Since it was unfeasible to guarantee a predation event at a specific time, to ensure the efficacy of the experiment and to strengthen the effects of the alarm cues, we created an extract from round goby skin containing alarm pheromones released from epidermal cells while fish are attacked/injured [97]. This allowed us to simulate the release of alarm signals without relying solely on spontaneous attacks by higher predators. The 30 donor round gobies in a size range of 71–90 mm ($81.3\text{ mm} \pm 5.5\text{ mm}$, $\text{TL} \pm \text{SD}$) were sacrificed by a blow to the head to prevent any potential interference in the release of chemical signals that could occur if anaesthetics were used. A skin fillet was carefully removed from both sides of each fish to obtain approximately 130.5 cm^2 of skin devoid of muscle tissue. All skin samples were promptly placed in 200 mL of distilled water, kept chilled on ice to prevent any decomposition until further processing, and homogenised. Subsequently, the homogenised samples were filtered through a glass-wool filter twice to remove any remaining particles (e.g., scales) and then diluted with distilled water to form a solution with a final concentration of 0.1 cm^2 of skin. mL^{-1} [61]. Subsequently, syringes with a volume of 5 mL were filled with the prepared extract and stored in the freezer at $-29\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ before use in experiments.

2.3. Experimental Design

Based on the modified methodology described by Richter et al. [98], as well as our own previous experiences, we set up a series of five experimental trials (see below) to examine the gastric evacuation rate and food consumption probability under three different treatments. These treatments involved exposing tested fish to different conditions: (a) conspecific alarm cues and kairomones released by a higher predator fed on round gobies (conspecific treatment; CS); (b) chemical cues released by a higher predator fed on earthworms (heterospecific treatment; HS); and (c) clear water devoid of any chemical stimulants (control treatment; C).

Each treatment was tested in a parallel trial (five repetitions) within a separate recirculation system comprising four vertically arranged tanks, each with a capacity of 400 L (RAS; $4 \times 400\text{ L}$). The uppermost and lowermost tanks were fitted with biological and mechanical filters in each system, respectively. Depending on the treatment, the upper tank was stocked either with seven European eels fed on round gobies (whose numbers were controlled by the end of each experimental trial; CS treatment), seven European eels fed on earthworms (HS treatment), or no European eels (chemical cue-free water; C treatment). The water containing specific chemical cues flowed into the second lower tank, where 11 experimental arenas per treatment were placed, i.e., 33 arenas for each experimental trial were used at the same time. Each experimental arena consisted of an aquarium (total volume of 6.5 L) divided into two parts by a glass wall with a lower steel mesh to maintain the water flow (Figure 1). The tested fish was placed in the larger section ($23.0 \times 19.5 \times 20\text{ cm}$) equipped with a half-cut pipe serving as a shelter and an upper outlet for water flow. The smaller section ($10 \times 23 \times 20\text{ cm}$) had an inlet for flowing water (Figure 1). Each aquarium was covered with a matte translucent film to minimise stress and disturbance and to prevent visual interactions between gobies.

Figure 1. Experimental arena. Black arrows mark water inflow and outflow, respectively.

Before each trial, a 36-h fasting period was imposed on the fish to ensure complete gut clearance and preclude any potential influence of the remains of the acclimatisation food on the experiment outcomes. To prevent possible cannibalism provoked by starvation and to ensure that a particular individual consumed a given amount of food, all fish were placed separately in experimental arenas. The light regime was set to 12 h light–12 h dark, including dusk and dawn simulations. The temperature was maintained at a constant rate throughout the experiment at 21.48 ± 0.026 °C; mean \pm SE. Automatic dataloggers Minikin T (EMS, Brno, Czech Republic) monitored the temperature every two hours.

To obtain the conspecific cues, 15 round gobies were introduced into the tanks where the eels had been feeding before the start of each trial. After each trial, tanks were replenished with gobies to ensure an equal number at the start of each trial. Following a 36-h starvation period, the round gobies were fed with the tested food (Food A) consisting of 12 *Chironomus* sp. larvae with an average whole portion weight of $0.074 \text{ g} \pm 0.023 \text{ g}$, ($W \pm \text{SD}$) (see Figure 2), which were used to observe the evacuation rate of the fish. After two hours, the tested food remains were removed from each aquarium, which marked the start of the main experimental phase and sampling. Fish that did not consume any test food within this period were excluded from the remaining part of the experiment. At this time, easily distinguishable food, marked as Food B, was given to the fish to observe the evacuation rate while continuous feeding was applied [99]. Simultaneously, the external stimulant, i.e., the predator odour from the upper tank and prepared alarm cues or distilled water, were added to the treatments to observe the consumption probability of food B and the effects of the chemical cues on the evacuation rate of food A. Thus, four individuals of *Gammarus fossarum* (food B) with an average whole portion weight of $0.069 \text{ g} \pm 0.062 \text{ g}$ ($W \pm \text{SD}$) were provided to all experimental round gobies. Tubes were placed in the aquariums to allow clean water or water containing chemicals from the eel tanks to flow in throughout the experiment. Simultaneously, the first dose (5 mL) of alarm cues (for the conspecific treatment) or distilled water (for the heterospecific and control treatments) was released. To ensure continuous exposure to the chemical signals, which have been shown to persist in aquatic environments for up to six hours [100], the prepared solutions were released repeatedly every four hours (Figure 2). The experimental arenas were checked simultaneously to ensure that constant food availability was being maintained.

Figure 2. Experimental setup. C, control treatment (supplied by clear water without any chemical cues derived from predator or prey), HS, heterospecific treatment (supplied by water from a tank with predator fed by common earthworms), CS, conspecific treatment (supplied by water from a tank with predator fed by round gobies); solid red lines depict the application of food A (*Chironomus* sp. larvae) and food B (*Gammarus fossarum*); the dashed line represents the removal of the remains of food A; blue arrows represent the hours at which the chemical alarm cues (skin extract from the round goby in CS treatment) or distilled water (in C and HS treatments), depending on the treatment, were applied; green arrows denote the time intervals after feeding with food B at which the tested fish were sampled.

Fish samples were taken at eight time intervals: 0, 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 16, and 24 h after feeding with food B (Figure 2). In total, we tested 144 fish specimens across five trials of the experiment, with six replications at each time point. When sampling each round goby, the number of prey individuals remaining (food B) in the experimental arena was counted to estimate the total amount of food consumed by the round goby individual over a given time. The collected fish were killed using the anaesthetic MS 222 and kept in a freezer at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis, conducted within two weeks of completing the experiment.

2.4. Sample Processing

Before determining the gut contents of the round goby individuals, several measurements were taken, including total length (TL; mm), standard length (SL; mm), body weight with a weighing accuracy of 0.01 g (*W*; g) (Kern and Sohn GmbH, Balingen, Germany), and sex determination [15]. Subsequently, each fish was dissected, with the gut extraction following the methodology outlined by Manko [101]. The extracted gut/intestine and its contents were weighed to an accuracy of 0.1 mg (EX224M analytical balance, Ohaus Corporation, Parsippany, NJ, USA). The length of the gut was measured, and the position of each food type (foods A and B) was observed. Next, the gut contents (food A and B separately) were placed on glass microfibre discs (type 691, 516–0862; VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA) that had been preheated in a laboratory chamber furnace (LAC-Ht40A1; LAC s.r.o., Židlochovice, Czech Republic) to completely decompose all organic carbon molecules (30 min at $500\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). All the microfibre discs were weighed (Mettler-Toledo Excellence Plus XP6 microbalance; Greifensee, Switzerland) before the gut content was placed upon them. The empty intestine was also weighed and subsequently placed on pre-numbered and weighed aluminium foil. The body of the de-gutted fish (portioned to ease the drying

process) was weighed (M3P, Sartorius, Goettingen, Germany) and placed on aluminium foil alongside the empty gut. Finally, samples of the gut contents (food A and B), the fish carcasses, and the empty dissected gut were dried overnight at 105 °C and stored in a desiccator to determine the dry weight (DW) using microbalances.

2.5. Data Analysis

All data analyses and graphical procedures were performed using R software (R Development Core Team, v. 4.1.1, Vienna, Austria).

2.5.1. Assumptions of Observation Independence

We tested the assumption that all 24 design-based groups represented by round goby individuals sampled at eight individual sampling time points for each treatment did not differ either in standard length (SL) or wet weight (WW). Generalised linear models (GLMs) were employed with Gamma distribution and a 'log' link function. In addition, the differences between these design-based groups in the counts of the quantity of food A consumed were performed using a GLM with Poisson distribution and the 'log' link function. Due to the underdispersion detected, a quasi-likelihood estimation method was applied.

2.5.2. Gut Evacuation Rate

The evacuation rate was estimated with statistical modelling of the weight of the prey remaining in the gut over time, whereby the relative gut content (GI) was calculated as a ratio of the dry weight (DW) of the tested food (food A) at the time of sampling vs. fish dry body weight. Subsequently, based on (GI), we computed the evacuation rate (R). This parameter can be described using linear and/or exponential functions [72,74]. Hence, given the uncertainty presented within the literature, we fitted our data to both linear Equation (1) and exponential Equation (2) models, represented by the following:

$$GI_t = GI_0 - Rt \quad (1)$$

$$GI_t = GI_0 e^{-Rt} \quad (2)$$

where GI_t is relative gut content at time t , GI_0 is the initial intestine content at postprandial time t_0 (h), and R is the gastric evacuation rate [74,102].

We fitted the equations using GLMs with Gaussian distributions; 'identity' and 'log' link functions were applied. We tested the relationship between the relative gut content GI used as a response variable and the explanatory variables: (I) 'time' (continuous numerical variable) and (II) 'treatment' (three-level factor). All zero values for the relative gut content were replaced by 0.0014 mg to represent half of the overall minimum gut content mass. The use of a Gaussian distribution was appropriate given that the histogram of model residuals was found to be close to the Gaussian; the assumption of homoscedasticity was also fulfilled. The quality of the model fits was expressed using the McFadden coefficient of determination (R^2). Regression coefficients for each treatment yielded by the model with the higher R^2 were taken as the individual evacuation rates.

2.5.3. Consumption Probability

To test differences between treatments at all time points in the consumption probability of offered prey (food B), we employed a GLM with a binomial distribution with the logistic link function. The proportions of eaten and offered prey were used as a response, and observations were weighted by counts of offered prey. Due to the detected overdispersion, a quasi-likelihood estimation method was applied.

3. Results

A total of 144 round goby individuals (SL = 55.2 ± 2.51 mm; wet weight WW = 3.79 ± 0.56 g; mean \pm SD) were tested during five experimental trials. Depending on the treatment, the round gobies were observed to eat 0.023 (C), 0.033 (CS), and 0.036 (HS) g of provided food B, which corresponds to 2.31% (C), 2.12% (CS), and 1.94% (HS) of the wet fish body weight.

3.1. Assumptions of Observation Independence

All 24 design-based groups were completely standardised in terms of round goby SL ($F_{23,120} = 0.93$, $p = 0.56$), WW ($F_{23,120} = 0.88$, $p = 0.63$), and amount of food A consumed ($F_{23,120} = 1.30$, $p = 0.18$).

3.2. Gut Evacuation Rate

The fit of the exponential GLM Equation (2) was better than the fit of the linear GLM Equation (1) when comparing their R^2 values (exponential model: $R^2 = 0.77$; linear model: $R^2 = 0.49$). Both linear and exponential GLMs revealed that the interaction between 'treatment \times time' (Model 1; Table 1) obtained by modelling the effects on *GI* was not significant ($p = 0.61$ and $p = 0.96$, respectively); thus, the evacuation rate was probably not influenced by the 'treatment'. A further exponential GLM with additive effects (Model 2; Table 1) revealed a significant effect for both 'treatment' ($F_{2,140} = 4.69$, $p = 0.01$) and 'time' ($F_{1,140} = 453.90$, $p < 0.001$) on *GI*. *GI* in CS was 23.7% higher than in C and 9.8% lower in C than in HS (Figure 3). Nevertheless, complete gut clearance in all treatments took 16 h (Figure 3). According to the 95% confidence interval overlap, the evacuation rate was the same ($R = 0.2323 \pm 0.011$ g·g⁻¹ fish·h⁻¹; mean \pm SE given as an absolute value) in all treatments (Figure 4), which corresponds to the fitted decrease in *GI* per hour (20.7%). Since the linear GLM with additive effects did not reveal any significant effect of the 'treatment' ($F_{2,140} = 1.43$, $p = 0.24$) and considering the low effect size of the 'treatment' in exponential GLM Model 2 (Table 1), it is doubtful that the 'treatment' had any impact on the *GI*.

Table 1. Relationships between relative gut content (*GI*) and the explanatory variables, i.e., 'treatment' and 'time'. A generalised linear model (GLM) with Gaussian distribution (with the log link function applied) was used to fit and test the relationships. The significances of all relationships were tested with partial *F*-tests. Asterisks following *p*-values denote significance: * 0.05, *** 0.001.

Model	Predictor	df	Deviance	F Value	p-Value	
Model 1: (<i>GI</i>) ~ Treatment \times Time						
	Treatment	2	0.0015	3.13	0.047	*
	Time	1	0.0034	1.56	<0.001	***
	Treatment \times Time	2	0.0014	0.04	0.964	
Residual df: = 138						
Model 2: (<i>GI</i>) ~ Treatment + Time						
	Treatment	2	0.0015	4.69	0.011	*
	Time	1	0.0061	453.91	<0.001	***
Residual df: = 140						

Figure 3. Relative gut content GI (computed as $DW \text{ food A} / DW \text{ fish}$) at the time after food application in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) under three experimental treatments: C, control treatment (no chemical cues); CS, conspecific treatment (conspecific alarm cues and kairomones released by a higher predator fed on round gobies); HS, heterospecific treatment (chemical cues released by a higher predator fed on earthworms).

Figure 4. Overlap between the 95% confidence intervals of the gastric evacuation rates (R ; mean \pm S.D., $n = 144$) of the tested round gobies under three experimental treatments: C, control treatment (no chemical cues); CS, conspecific treatment (conspecific alarm cues and kairomones released by a higher predator fed on round goby individuals); HS, heterospecific treatment (chemical cues released by a higher predator fed on earthworms).

3.3. Consumption Probability

There were no significant effects of the interaction ‘treatment \times time’ ($F_{12,105} = 0.59$, $p = 0.85$) (Table 2), as well as ‘treatment’ ($F_{2,117} = 1.86$, $p = 0.16$) or ‘time’ ($F_{6,117} = 1.20$, $p = 0.31$) (Table 2), indicating that the presence of the chemical stimulants did not significantly influence the probability of food B being consumed.

Table 2. Relationship between food consumption probability of food B (eaten and offered prey was used as a response, and observations were weighted by counts of offered prey) and explanatory variables, i.e., ‘treatment’ and ‘time’. The table depicts two models: one includes the interaction between explanatory variables (Treatment \times Time), while the second, additive effects of predictors (Treatment + Time). A generalised linear model (GLM) with quasibinomial distribution was used to fit and test the relationships. The significances of all relationships were tested with partial *F*-tests.

Model	Predictor	<i>df</i>	Deviance	<i>F</i> Value	<i>p</i> -Value
Food B consumption ~ Treatment \times Time					
	Treatment	2	347.82	1.0178	0.3649
	Time	6	352.13	0.5607	0.7607
	Treatment \times Time	12	364.15	0.5884	0.8473
Residual <i>df</i> : = 105					
Food B consumption ~ Treatment + Time					
	Treatment	2	375.73	1.8609	0.1601
	Time	6	386.55	1.1994	0.3115
Residual <i>df</i> : = 117					

4. Discussion

Our study revealed no discernible response in the invasive round goby to exposure to either type of chemical stimuli, and the feeding behaviour of the experimental groups subjected to different treatments was unaffected. The results of our experiment did not confirm the expected differences, including a decrease in the tested parameters due either to the presence of the predator’s odour or the chemical alarm signals received from injured conspecifics.

Despite the slightly lower amount of food B eaten in the HS treatment compared to the CS treatment (and especially C), all tested round gobies consistently processed and evacuated prey at the same rates per unit of time in all treatments, which is a surprising finding that contradicts our expectations. Considering that food processing (here represented by the evacuation rate) can be influenced by a multitude of factors including food properties [103,104] and predator and prey biometric characteristics [72,105–107], as well as by environmental conditions [108–111], we anticipated some variation between treatments. For instance, the presence of predators and their direct chemical recognition can lead to physiological activity changes [58,112] including alterations in hormone levels such as cortisol [113,114], as occurs in the case of conspecific disturbance or alarm cues [62]. In the context of our study, these physiological responses could be attributable to food intake and gut evacuation rates that are modified as stress-induced behaviour. However, although they did not differ, the treatment and time did seem to have a significant impact on the relative gut content. Nevertheless, considering the (i) small size of the statistical effect of the treatment, (ii) the lack of differences in the counts of consumed prey and fish biometrics between treatments, and (iii) the observation that all tested fish experienced complete gut clearance within 16 h regardless of the applied cues, we consider that the biological effect of treatment on the *GI* was negligible.

As for the evacuation rate, no significant differences were observed in the counts of the consumed prey (food B) (as given by the tested consumption probability). This also contradicts our expectations, as previous studies have demonstrated suppressed feeding activity including decreases in foraging and consumption rates under predator-induced stress conditions [62,87,115,116], as well as feeding latency [86] or even a complete cessation of food intake, as reported in the studies conducted by Giaquinto and Hoffmann [117]. However, since the complete reduction of food intake observed in the pintado catfish *Pseudoplatystoma corruscans* (Spix and Agassiz, 1829) was a result of the exposure to chemosensory information from non-injured conspecifics [117], we should question which alarm signals—i.e., disturbance or *shreckstoff*—are most important in overall conspecific

communication. On the other hand, Fraser and Huntingford [118] proposed that foragers may exhibit various responses to danger, with 'risk-reckless' behaviour being one such mechanism whereby individuals ignore exposed hazards while maintaining maximum feeding levels regardless of food abundance. Our study sheds light on the behaviour of round gobies within this framework and suggests that it is an adaptation aiding its invasiveness success [119]. This behaviour matches previous research on round goby boldness [120–122] and how this trait influences its foraging ability [123,124]. It also facilitates the effective exploitation of available food resources with a visible superiority of bolder individuals over shy ones when it comes to resource usage [125] when invading new areas. While bold behaviour is often observed in specimens at the invasion front and is more characteristic of new populations rather than established ones [126], it is notable that bold fish also exhibit a smaller size-at-age compared to shy fish [127], which agrees with the overall size distribution of our tested fish population. Nevertheless, the inability to effectively balance predator avoidance behaviour with other fitness-related activities such as foraging may compromise fish survival and overall fitness, particularly in established populations [61,77,128]. Therefore, it is crucial to undertake further studies examining additional behavioural responses, shelter usage patterns, and potential shifts in round goby activity when encountering predators.

Given the existing evidence—i.e., increased respiratory responses [129]—that round gobies are responsive to chemical stimuli (specifically, injury-released alarm signals from conspecifics), we should examine whether or not the properties of the chemical cues and the intensity of the applied stimulants in our study were sufficient to elicit a response from the tested organisms. Our stimulus preparation followed the methodology outlined by Wisenden et al. [61] that uses the whole skin subjected to mechanical processing and extraction. The issue is whether another method [130] involving skin incisions washed with water could be more effective, as found in responses primarily in minnows. Many previous studies have shown that the magnitude of reactions in fish increases with the concentration of cues—e.g., in goldfish *Carassius auratus* (Linnaeus, 1758) exposed to dietary cues from a predator [131]—where variations in concentrations may indicate different degrees of threat [132]. Moreover, it seems that the frequency of the application of the alarm substance might also influence outcomes if we compare our results to those from studies of the behavioural response of the monkey goby *Neogobius fluviatilis* (Pallas, 1814) [133]. Continuous dosing with damage-released alarm cues (skin extract) in these studies may have given more potent effects than in our experiment in which the extract was only applied every four hours. However, we believe that our application time interval was sufficient since Hazlett [100] has reported that alarm cues fade from water within six hours; other studies have shown that the biological activities of injury-released chemical alarm cues in minnows and amphipods last for 3–6 h at 18 °C [134]. Even so, the round goby could be a less sensitive species characterised by a higher threshold regarding concentrations of alarm cues and/or the frequency of stimuli required to activate an expected response. Hence, other characteristics such as the persistence of the stimulus should be taken into account since multiple environmental conditions may influence particle breakdown and the degradation of alarm cues (solar radiation, temperature, pH, or oxygen levels) [130]. However, these factors may not be applicable to our study since we conducted them under laboratory conditions in which all parameters were maintained constant throughout the experiment. Since Chivers et al. [130] observed a decrease in the strength of the reaction intensity after 30 min, it seems that the initial application of the stimulants is key and each further application could acclimatise fish further to the chemical signal.

The sensitivity of fish in perceiving the threat signal is thus probably key. Responses to olfactory cues require the ability to perceive the specific intensity (concentration) of the odorants that compose the stimuli [135]. The sensitivity of olfactory receptors to specific chemicals varies between species, with observed specific threshold concentrations for cues [68] and fish at individual levels [136]. Specific variation is closely related to the anatomy and morphology of the olfactory organ [137], and a histochemical study

has confirmed the widespread presence of olfactory sensory neurons in the peripheral olfactory organ, which underlines the crucial role of chemosensory signalling in round goby survival [138]. Thus, we anticipated that our tested fish would respond to the odour of predators as well as to alarm cues. Nonetheless, the whole Gobiidae family (Actinopterygii), which is known for the diversified production of alarm substances [139], exhibits variations in responses to chemical alarm communications despite the presence of epidermal club cells associated with such responses [140,141], a rule that our research seems to confirm. Thus, we believe that along with the perception threshold, another possible explanation of our observations may relate to the fact that chemical cue recognition in round gobies requires more experience and learning, as has been observed in many other fish [81,142]. Utne-Palm [143] claims that the recognition of odour in two-spotted gobies *Gobiusculus flavescens* (Fabricius, 1779) requires experience and that predator identities can be rapidly learnt by associating the smell of a predator with those of a prey chemical cue [144].

Regardless of the production of alarm substances, we did still expect to observe a reaction to the predator odour in the heterospecific treatment since the used prey was not in any way phylogenetically related to or belonged to the same prey guild [70,145–158]. However, unlike many invertebrates and amphibians, most fish are innately unable to recognise their predators' kairomones, the exception being some groups such as salmonids [49,149]. Kairomones become associated with risk through direct exposure to alarm cues during a predatory attack or through the detection of dietary cues through passive [150], or even active [151], sampling behaviour during predator inspection. The ability of fish to respond to predators may not necessarily result from their ability to detect predator odours directly but rather from their ability to detect chemical alarm signals produced by conspecifics or heterospecifics in their diets. This has been confirmed in research on the pearl cichlid *Geophagus brasiliensis* (Quoy and Gaimard, 1824) by Arvigo et al. [69], which showed that predator odours did not induce any antipredator response. Similarly, the frillfin goby *Bathygobius soporator* (Valenciennes, 1837) is known to be indifferent to predator odours, although conspecific cues do affect its ventilation rate activity [66]. When exposed to predator odours and visual cues, the two-spotted goby likewise does not exhibit any innate anti-predator response [143].

On the other hand, research has demonstrated that even a single exposure to predator cues can enhance the learning process, thereby enabling fish to retain recognition of predators for extended periods and providing survival benefits. For instance, brook trout *Salvelinus fontinalis* (Mitchill, 1814) trained to recognise predators such as the chain pickerel *Esox niger* (Lesueur, 1818) have higher survival rates than untrained individuals [70]. Furthermore, learning could also play a critical role in acquiring experience with particular fish species and is required if the expected responses to predator cues are to be generated. However, given that the round goby and the European eel co-exist in the round goby source locality, we anticipate that a certain experience level would already have been established.

Our findings indicate that round gobies did not show any response to chemical stimuli from predatory odours combined with alarm substances, particularly those from conspecifics. This contradicts all expectations, as some fish species react to alarm substances produced by other species [152], with the most vital reactions typically provided by conspecific alarm substances [153]. However, little is known about fish anti-predator responses when predator and alarm cues are combined [69]. To date, anti-predator responses to the stimulants tested separately have been extensively studied in numerous fish species [60,65,154,155] showing that different types of chemical stimulants often induce different and specific responses [69]. Given this consideration, our approach using both chemical stimulants together may represent a limitation, so examining each stimulant separately could potentially provide a more complete understanding of the round goby's chemical perceptions since one of the chemical cues might mitigate the impact of the other (although in this case, we believe it to be unlikely). However, it is essential to acknowledge that under natural conditions, chemical signals consist of a complex mixture of compounds conveying specific risk information [136,140]. Signals transmitted by predators combined

with cues released during the digestion process can provide further detailed knowledge regarding the abundance, location, and recent feeding habits of predators in their environment [56]. Therefore, our method produced robust results, which may agree well with field-related conditions.

Most importantly, although our study did not reveal any changes in the food processing consumed between the tested groups, it is essential to emphasise that round gobies maintained consistently high evacuation rates regardless of the presence of higher predators. Combined with a previous study [99], these findings confirm the great efficiency of round gobies in processing and digesting food when continuously fed, particularly on chironomids. Given that evacuation rates closely regulate feeding rates [76], the rapid evacuation of chironomid larvae suggests potentially high predatory pressure on these macrozoobenthos taxa, present in the round goby diet [31,95,96], which could lead to modifications in benthic community composition and reduced resource availability for other consumers [23]. This trait, allied with the boldness of the round goby—i.e., obviously low sensitivity to predation danger—might suggest a potential competitive advantage over other local native species when colonising new ecosystems. For instance, compared to the ruffe *Gymnocephalus cernua* (Linnaeus, 1758), whose population decline has been linked to the appearance of this goby [36,156] as well as to a temporal collapse in ruffe populations [35,157], the round goby evacuates chironomid larvae faster under similar thermal conditions as those used in our studies. Moreover, the high predator-threat sensitivity in ruffes [158] suggests that the round goby could outcompete other species for food resources when introduced into a new environment, irrespective of the threat from local top predators.

Our results indicate that other stimulants such as visual perception might be relevant in the sensory hierarchy of this fish and play the role of a starter in combination with chemical cues, as previously confirmed [143,159]. Interestingly, some studies conducted on other gobiids, e.g., two-spotted gobies exposed to both visual and chemical stimuli from their natural predators, have proven that in some of the cases, additional visual predator exposures can sometimes strengthen anti-predator responses to chemical cues [143]. This confirms the importance of the interaction between both types of stimulants, as has been reported in other studies [63,84,85]. Thus, we believe that further studies involving visual cues and different concentrations of chemical stimuli and application methods should be prioritised to obtain a better overview of round goby feeding behaviour and prey–predator dynamics within local ecosystems.

Since fish, including round gobies, use olfaction not only to avoid predators but also to find food, orientate themselves, and reproduce [160–162], we anticipated that our tested fish would actively employ olfaction for predator recognition. The failure of our hypothesis underscores the complexity of predator–prey interactions and adaptation mechanisms. While many aquatic animals recognise predators via chemical cues and respond adaptively [163], in invasive or introduced species this ability seems to be reduced, which can provide an advantage when exploiting local resources. This can potentially also lead to competitive disadvantages in predator-rich environments, but if the visual cues permit a rapid response to a threat, the cost may not be so great. Therefore, understanding the perception and management of predation threats by invasive species deepens our insight into the factors driving the rapid invasion of unfamiliar habitats by some species, while others do not exhibit such behaviours.

5. Conclusions

In conclusion, our study sheds light on the behaviour of the invasive round goby concerning its response to chemical stimuli from predators and injured conspecifics. Contrary to expectations, round gobies did not exhibit discernible reactions to these cues, maintaining consistent feeding behaviour regardless of predator presence. This suggests species-specific thresholds in perceiving chemical cues, highlighting the complexity of predator–prey interactions and adaptation mechanisms. Further research involving visual

cues and different concentrations of chemical stimuli should be prioritized to understand better round goby feeding efficiency and behaviour while including prey–predator dynamics in invaded ecosystems. Understanding the perception and management of predation threats by invasive species is crucial for elucidating factors driving their rapid invasion of new habitats, thus contributing to more effective conservation and management strategies.

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CHAPTER 4

FROM SIGHT TO SMELL: DOES THE VISUAL AND OLFACTORY EXPOSURE TO HIGHER PREDATOR MITIGATE FEEDING ACTIVITY IN INVASIVE ROUND GOBY *NEOGOBIOUS MELANOSTOMUS*?

Szydłowska, N.Z., Buřič, M., Let, M., Kubec, J., Drozd, B. From sight to smell: does the visual and olfactory exposure to higher predator mitigate feeding and activity in invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*? Manuscript.

My share on this work was about 60%.

From sight to smell: does the visual and olfactory exposure to higher predator mitigate feeding activity in invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*?

Natalia Z. Szydłowska*, Marek Let, Jan Kubec, Miloš Buřič, Bořek Drozd

South Bohemian Research Center of Aquaculture and Biodiversity of Hydrocenoses, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice, Zátěš 728/II, 389 25 Vodňany, Czech Republic

Highlights:

- Exposure to predator presence significantly affected the feeding activity of the round goby.
- The round goby showed the strongest response to combined visual and chemical predator cues, resulting in reduced foraging.
- The round goby appeared unresponsive to chemical stimuli alone.
- No significant interaction was found between visual and chemical cues in the round goby's food intake.
- Regardless of type of experimental treatment, the round goby remained an efficient predator.

Abstract

Invasive species, including the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*), pose significant threats to freshwater ecosystems, affecting local biodiversity and food webs. This study investigates the impact of higher predator presence on the foraging behavior and food consumption of the round goby, focusing on the role of visual and chemical cues in early risk detection. We conducted a series of experiments on the round goby as a mesopredator to assess food intake under varying predation risk scenarios (VIS – visual exposure to top predator, CH – top predator smell, VISCH – both stimuli, C – control, no stimuli). The results indicate that round goby consumed an average of 10.34 ± 6.11 prey items individuals, where the lowest consumption was observed in the VISCH treatment, with only 20.09% of chironomid larvae consumed ($n=6.03 \pm 5.66$ larvae individuals). Interestingly, even the mixed treatment indicated variations in prey consumption, there was no significant interaction between the chemical and visual stimuli ($X^2=0.03$, $p=0.87$). Visual cues significantly increased total prey mortality ($X^2=30.64$, $p<0.001$), whereas chemical cues did not show a significant effect on prey consumption ($X^2=3.08$, $p=0.08$). Our findings suggest that visual detection plays a critical role in the round goby's anti-predatory behavior. Considering the overall nocturnal activity and biology of the investigated invader, along with potential environmental limitations such as reduced light and increased turbidity, the overall adaptation revealed in our studies appears questionable in nature. Therefore, we believe that our findings underscore the need for further research on predator-prey interactions in invaded freshwater ecosystems, including the learning process by the multiple exposure to chemical stimuli (predator odors or alarm cues) to better understand the implications for local biodiversity and inform management strategies.

Keywords: vision, chemical communication, predator-prey interaction, food intake, risk recognition, European perch

Introduction

Despite the numerous multidisciplinary studies conducted in the field of biological invasions—covering life-history traits (Lawson and Hill, 2021), reproductive traits (Dashminov and Puzunova, 2021), experimental approaches (Roche et al., 2021), and others—invasion science remains an evolving field with many mechanisms still not fully understood or uncovered. A typical and prominent example is a non-native fish – round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*, Pallas 1814), which is recognized as one of the most widespread invaders, listed among the 100 worst invaders in Europe (Vilà et al., 2009; Hirsch et al., 2016) and has become a significant subject of interest in numerous laboratory and field investigations over recent decades (reviewed in Kornis et al., 2012; Cerwenka et al., 2023). The round goby has rapidly established large populations following its initial introduction (Corkum et al., 2004; Johnson et al., 2005) and expanded its range, invading various regions, including the Great Lakes of North America (Jude et al., 1992; Ricciardi and Maclsaac, 2000), as well as river systems in Central and Western Europe (Jurajda et al., 2005; Manné et al., 2013; Roche et al., 2013). Following its introduction, the round goby has caused significant disturbances and changes within local food webs by primarily exerting considerable pressure on benthic invertebrate populations, which serve as a key food source (Mikl et al., 2017a; Oesterwind et al., 2017). Concurrently, as a new mesopredator in these ecosystems, the round goby has quickly become a crucial food source for various native predators (Jacobs et al., 2010; Taraborelli et al., 2010; Lenhardt et al., 2011). Despite extensive research documenting predation on the round goby (Hirsch et al., 2016), there is still limited knowledge regarding how higher predators indirectly affect the behaviour and activity of this mesopredator (round goby), particularly in relation to resource prey (Palacios et al., 2015).

Understanding prey-predator interactions, particularly the behavioural and activity changes resulting from local predation risk, requires a detailed exploration of species' abilities to detect and respond to such risks—abilities that are crucial for survival (Berejikian et al., 2003; Sih et al., 2010). Prey species rely on various sensory cues (Mathis and Smith, 1993; Brown et al., 2003), including stress-induced signals from predator-prey interactions, to adjust their behaviour—such as altering foraging patterns or seeking shelter—thereby minimizing exposure to threats (Hettzey et al., 2015).

Following that, prey can rely on variety of stimuli including chemical, visual, acoustic or mechanosensory cues (Holmes and McCormick, 2010; Lukas et al., 2021), each providing different level of accuracy, e.g. predator's presence, identity or proximity (Dessborn et al., 2012; Bhattacharyya et al., 2017). Overall, in teleosts, both vision and chemical communication are recognised as the primary ones for identifying threats (Karplus and Algom, 1981; Wisenden, 2000), though the relative importance of each can vary among species (Santacà et al., 2021). Research has demonstrated that importance of two senses differs among taxa, where each fish species prioritize sensory cues based on their unique ecological and behavioral adaptations. For instance, zebrafish *Danio rerio* (Hamilton, 1822) rely more heavily on olfactory cues, while guppies *Poecilia reticulata* Peters, 1859 are more attuned to visual signals (Santacà et al., 2021). As ecosystems facing many disturbances and changes—such as light intensity, turbidity, or habitat complexity (Hansen et al., 2013; Zanghi and Ioannou, 2024)—visual communication can become compromised, where nocturnal species often depend on tactile, chemical, and electric senses to function effectively in low-light environments (Teichmann, 1954; Atta, 2013). Following that, chemical communication is considered to be the most reliable and universal, serving as a primary source of information in aquatic ecosystems for assessing risks and avoiding predators (Smith, 1986; Chivers and Smith, 1998; Kats and Dill, 1998; Ferrari et al., 2010), irrespectively to the environmental conditions. Infochemicals, which serve as a key

form of chemical communication, have two main sources (Brönmark and Hansson, 2000) including substances released by prey in distress, such as alarm cues from heterospecifics or injured conspecifics (Chivers and Smith, 1998; Brown 2003; Culumber, 2015), and substances directly released by predators (Miyai et al., 2016).

On the contrary, many species seem to rely heavily on vision (Santacà et al., 2021), with visual cues being particularly important in gobies (family Gobiidae, Actinopterygii) (Utne and Bacchi, 1997; Utne-Palm, 2001). This may be due to differences in chemical cue production in their epidermis, as not all species have developed these structures (Pfeiffer, 1977). However, responses to chemical cues, including alarm substances, are not always guaranteed by the presence of these skin adaptations, highlighting the complexity and adaptability of their sensory strategies (Smith, 1992; Marsh-Hunkin et al., 2013). This demonstrates that fish can adjust their sensory reliance based on both species-specific traits and the environmental context in which they find themselves.

Given its ecological role as a non-native invasive mesopredator in freshwater ecosystems, understanding the round goby's interactions with fish predators across trophic levels is crucial. Although numerous studies have examined anti-predatory behaviors in gobies (Smith, 1989; Smith and Lawrence, 1992; McCormick and Manassa, 2008; Marsh-Hunkin et al., 2013), the influence of higher-level predators on round goby foraging behavior and the role of specific sensory cues in early predation risk detection remain poorly understood. While there is evidence that round gobies may adapt to using chemical cues (Pütys et al., 2015), the role of individual sensory modalities and interactions between them (Mathis et al., 1993; Bouwma and Hazlett, 2001) in behaviors like foraging are still unclear. Further research is therefore necessary to fully understand these risk-detection mechanisms, round goby behavior in natural environments, and its impact on benthic invertebrate communities in invaded areas. To address these gaps, our laboratory studies aimed to 1) examine an influence of local predation risk by top predator on the food consumption and feeding behaviour of the round goby; 2) identify which sensory cues are most critical for early risk detection and triggering anti-predatory responses such as reduced foraging.

Following the above mentioned, we hypothesized that: 1. Exposure to higher/top predator presence will significantly reduce the food consumption of mesopredators, leading to increased mortality of the provided prey. This is expected to occur due to the trade-offs between predator avoidance and other fitness-related activities, resulting in less time spent in the feeding area by mesopredators; 2. Visual cues will play a significant role in the round goby in predator detection and recognition, leading to variations in food consumption across different treatments.

Materials and methods

Experimental animals capture and maintenance

Individuals of the round goby, serving as a model non-native meso-predator species in our study, were captured using a backpack pulsed-DC electrofishing unit (FEG 1500, EFKO, Leutkirch, Germany) at their recent occurrence sites in the Elbe River (Děčín, North Bohemia, CZ; GPS: 50.7802267N, 14.2073869E) (Buřič et al., 2015; Roche et al., 2015). Subsequently, all experimental fish were transported to the experimental facility of FFPW USB in České Budějovice, Czech Republic, where the experiments were performed as well, respectively. The fish were acclimatized and stocked in a recirculating aquaculture system (RAS; 1600 l). During the acclimatization period, they were fed with frozen chironomid larvae. The basic physical-chemical water properties, including water temperature (19.43 ± 0.03 °C), oxygen saturation

($96.78 \pm 0.45\%$), and pH (7.25 ± 0.02), were monitored daily (HQ40d digital multimeter; Hach Lange GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany).

Native higher/top predator individuals of the European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*, Linnaeus, 1758) in a size ($n=36$; $SL=20.57 \pm 2.25$ cm; $\text{mean} \pm \text{S.D.}$) proved to feed on small size fishes including the round goby in the invaded localities (Almqvist et al., 2010; Rakauskas et al., 2013; Mikl et al., 2017b), as well as based on their mutual sympatric occurrence in the Elbe River were acquired using same electrofishing methods. All fish were acclimatized in two separate recirculating system (RAS; 1600l) for at least one week prior experiment for getting used on the daily offered prey. The water quality parameters in this system were also daily controlled ($T=19.83 \pm 0.02$ °C; $O_2=96.99 \pm 0.44\%$; $\text{pH}=7.23 \pm 0.02$; $\text{mean} \pm \text{SE}$).

The round gobies during the experiment were provided with a diet of *Chironomus* sp. larvae, consistent with their known dietary preferences (Phillips et al., 2003; Števove and Kováč, 2016; Všetíčková et al., 2018; Szydłowska et al., 2024a). The larvae were purchased from a pet store.

Experimental setup

All experiments were performed between 18–30 July 2023 following the methods of Berchtold and Côté (2020), as well as our previous experience from already performed studies (Szydłowska et al., 2024b) in order to examine the food consumption as well as fish behaviour and activity involved exposing tested fish to different conditions, i.e.: control treatment with no stimuli (C), exposure to visual cues (VIS), chemical cues (CH) or both stimuli (VISCH), respectively.

Each experimental run utilized six separate panels (Figure 1), with each panel comprising two main experimental areas (Arena_1), each containing two experimental aquaria placed side by side and isolated by Styrofoam screens.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a single experimental panel setup. Each panel comprises different experimental treatments (VIS, CH, VISCH) and a control setup (C), separated by an opaque wall. During the experiments, all panels were enclosed with black fabric to avoid external disturbances.

Each panel thus had a total of 24 experimental arenas, where 12 of them were designated for treatment (VIS, CH, VISCH) conditions and 12 for control (C) conditions. Fish were individually acclimated in their respective arenas for 12 h prior to experiment, following a 12 h fasting period (24 h of starvation total) to standardize hunger level. Each experimental arena consisted of an aquarium with a total volume of 6.5L, divided into two sections by a glass wall with a lower steel mesh to facilitate water flow. The larger section (23.0×19.5×20 cm) contained a half-cut pipe serving as both a shelter and feeding zone, while the smaller section (10×23×20 cm) was equipped with an aeration tube and used for chemical cue application to minimize disturbance of fish. To exclude any additional visual stimuli among conspecifics and thus additional stress, sidewalls of each adjacent arena with stocked round goby were covered with an opaque waterproof translucent plastic film, respectively. The light regime was set to 12 h light: 12 h dark, including dusk and dawn simulations. The temperature was maintained at a constant condition throughout the experiment at 20.18±0.02 °C (mean±SE). Automatic dataloggers Minikin T (EMS, Brno, Czech Republic) monitored the temperature every two hours, where additionally prior and post experimental control water parameter measurements were made.

In total, 3 series of experiments were conducted, each in three trials (with 24 repetitions per trial). Each experimental series was represented by different experimental treatment tested separately. The control conditions in our study were defined as those that measured how round goby responded to the same level or type of disturbance caused by the experimental procedure, but without the application of any tested stimuli. These conditions are outlined below (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Experimental design: a) Exposure to visual cues (VIS) and control (C) conditions, where the removal of the opaque wall started the experiment; b) Exposure to chemical cues represented by the predator odour (CH) and control (C) conditions; c) Exposure to both stimuli (visual and chemical) simultaneously (VISCH) and control (C) conditions, where the removal of the opaque wall started the experiment.

a) Visual cues effect:

Single higher/top predator, the European perch, was stocked in a glass-made tank (50x25x30 cm, V=30 L) enabling free movement and unobstructed visibility of the higher predator to tested mesopredator (round goby). Two round goby individuals were stocked separately to the experimental arenas set opposite to the main tank with the European perch. Initially, the tank containing the perch and the arenas with the round gobies were separated by opaque material, which was removed at the start of the experiment to allow visual exposure to the predator. For the control condition, a tank filled only with a clear water was placed in the same position in front of two experimental arenas with mesopredator (Figure 2a). No chemical communication between the predator and mesopredator was possible.

b) Olfactory cues effect:

To ensure the complete evacuation of prey-derived dietary cues, perch was fasted for 2 days prior to the experiment (Griffiths, 1976). This fasting ensured that the water collected from the tank contained only predator-derived olfactory cues. Prior to each trial, 15 to 20 perch were housed in a tank with non-flowing aerated water (250 L) overnight. Predator odour was introduced into the experimental arena by a 50% water exchange from the perch tank, while control conditions involved adding an equal volume of clear tapped water. Visual contact between the predator and mesopredator was impossible in this setup (Figure 2b).

c) Mixed (olfactory and visual) cues effect:

This experimental setup combined both visual and olfactory cues. Both types of stimuli (visual and olfactory) were introduced simultaneously into the experimental arenas, as mentioned above, respectively (Figure 2c).

In all treatments, observations commenced with the introduction of food (30 chironomid larvae) to the mesopredator, i.e. round goby. The induction of the specific stimulus occurred 10 minutes after the food was provided, marking the start of the experiment. Consistent with the increased consumption of chironomid larvae by round goby (Carman et al., 2006), experiment was conducted for six hours (07:00–13:00) of total duration, respectively.

Data Collection

Termination of each experimental trial was followed by fish biometric measurements, including total length (TL; mm), standard length (SL; mm), body weight with a weighing accuracy of 0.01 g (*W*; g) (Kern and Sohn GmbH, Balingen, Germany), and sex determination (Kornis et al., 2012). Additionally, we quantified the number of uneaten chironomid larvae within the experimental arenas to assess the feeding success of each tested round goby individual. The remaining preys were further classified as attacked prey (dead by the injury from the mesopredator with visible attack marks) or survived alive prey, respectively.

Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were performed using R Studio (version 3.6.1, R Development Core Team, 2019). A significance level of $\alpha < 0.05$ was applied for all statistical tests. The descriptive statistics below are presented as mean \pm standard deviation.

Assumptions of the observation independence

To investigate if there were differences in fish size between any pair of nine experimental groups (defined by the number of experimental runs) and between treatments (C, VIS, CH, VISCH), we used Generalised Linear Models (GLMs) with a Gamma distribution and a 'log' link function. The response variables analyzed included standard length (SL), and wet weight (W). These models assume independence of observations, which is crucial for accurate inference and validity of the results.

Effects of treatments on total mortality of prey

We employed Generalised Linear Mixed-Effect Models (GLMMs) with the binomial distribution and logistic link function to test potential effects of two binary factors, i.e. absence/presence of (i) VIS and (ii) CH treatments, their interaction (VISCH), and the control (C) with absence of both, on total mortality of prey offered to round goby. The response variable was the proportion of prey that were considered dead relative to the total number of offered prey (30 individuals), with the each observations weighted by the number of offered prey. Dead prey is represented by sum of counts of (i) prey killed through direct consumption (consumed prey) and (ii) prey attacked (being injured). Significant random effects were also included in the final model to account for variability among main experimental arenas (Arena_1), consisting of both experimental aquaria, and individual fish observations (OBS_ID – modelling the overdispersion). To further investigate the significance of differences among treatment levels, a pairwise comparisons method was applied. Estimated marginal means (EMMs) were calculated for each treatment level, and Tukey's adjustment method was used to test the significance of differences between these individual levels.

Effects of treatments on three-type prey responses

Cumulative Link Mixed Models (CLMM) with a logistic link function were applied to assess the significance of the effects of the VIS and CH treatments and their interaction (VISCH) described above on three ordinal response variables, including the counts of prey that (i) survived (i.e. were not killed and not eaten), (ii) were attacked (i.e. were killed but not eaten), or were consumed (i.e. were both killed and eaten). The identities of OBS_ID and Arena_1 were included as factors with random effects.

Results

The series of experiments provided detailed data on food intake for 216 round goby individuals. On average, 10.34 ± 6.11 prey items were consumed, accounting for 34.46% of the total prey provided, where the food intake of round goby varied between treatments. The highest consumption of chironomid larvae was observed for C treatment (41.67% of chironomid larvae consumed; $n=12.50 \pm 5.40$ larvae individuals), and the lowest consumption was observed for VISCH treatment (20.09% of chironomid larvae consumed; $n=6.03 \pm 5.66$ larvae individuals) (Table 1). A similar pattern was observed for the average number of prey attacked or injured (Table 1).

Observation independence assumptions

The round goby individuals had a mean SL of 68.45 ± 3.52 mm and a mean W of 5.84 ± 1.19 g. The fish size was uniform throughout all experiments (Table 1).

Table 1. Mean total length (TL), standard length (SL), and wet weight (W) of the tested round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) individuals used in each experimental treatment, and the average number of *Chironomus sp.* larvae consumed and attacked during the six hours experiments. Data presented as mean \pm S.D.

Treatment	TL [mm]	SL [mm]	W [g]	Consumed prey [n]	Attacked prey [n]
C	79.50 \pm 3.77	68.67 \pm 3.38	5.96 \pm 1.18	12.5 \pm 5.4	1.38 \pm 1.72
VIS	79.06 \pm 4.32	68.39 \pm 3.88	5.86 \pm 1.28	7.67 \pm 7.06	0.94 \pm 1.47
CH	79.17 \pm 3.94	68.81 \pm 3.90	5.87 \pm 1.24	10.7 \pm 4.08	1.00 \pm 1.1
VISCH	78.31 \pm 3.28	67.53 \pm 3.14	5.45 \pm 1.05	6.03 \pm 5.66	0.53 \pm 0.81

The interaction between treatment \times run was not significant for either biometric measure (SL: $F_{3,211}=0.99$, $p=0.40$; W: $F_{3,208}=0.83$, $p=0.48$). The analysis showed that the standard length (SL) and weight (W) of the tested round goby individuals did not differ significantly between the different treatments (SL: $F_{3,211}=0.99$, $p=0.39$; W: $F_{3,211}=1.10$, $p=0.35$) or across the nine experimental runs (SL: $F_{1,211}=0.05$, $p=0.82$; W: $F_{1,211}=2.38$, $p=0.12$).

The analysis revealed no significant differences in the tested fish biometric parameters across experimental conditions, indicating general uniformity. Although the overall treatment effect on W was non-significant, the VISCH treatment showed a significant non-zero coefficient according to z-statistics ($estimate=-0.24$, $p=0.03$). This suggests a possible difference in fish weight for this specific treatment. However, given the overall non-significant treatment effect tested by F-test, this finding should be considered preliminary and interpreted with caution.

Effects of treatments on total mortality of prey

There was a significant partial effect of visual cues of the predator ($X^2_1=30.64$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that the visual presence of predator significantly increased the likelihood of total prey mortality (Figure 3). Nevertheless, the significant partial main effect of the chemical cues did not play a significant role ($X^2_1=3.08$, $p=0.08$), suggesting that the presence of these chemical cues of predator origin did not affect prey consumption and injury rates (Figure 3). Besides that, the interaction between chemical \times visual stimuli did not show any significant effect ($X^2_1=0.03$, $p=0.87$), indicating that the combination of chemical and visual cues of predator did not significantly influence the total mortality of prey more than individual treatment did.

Figure 3. Total mortality probability of prey offered to round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*). Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals around mean estimates. Treatments are shown as the absence/presence of (i) visual cues (VIS), (ii) chemical cues (CH), and their interaction. Asterisk bracket following approximal p-values represent different significance levels between treatments: * 0.05, ** 0.01, *** 0.001; 'ns' indicates non-significant differences.

Pairwise comparisons revealed significant differences between several treatment pairs (Figure 3). Specifically, significant differences were observed between C and VISCH treatments ($p < 0.001$), CH and VISCH treatments ($p < 0.001$), as well as between CH and VIS treatments ($p = 0.04$) (Figure 3). The difference between C and CH treatments was not significant ($p = 0.56$) (Figure 3). The highest average mortality per arena was observed within the C treatment where $n = 13.09 \pm 2.52$ larvae individuals were killed by direct predation and attacks, whereas the lowest mortality of *Chironomus* sp. prey was detected within the VISCH treatment ($n = 6.06 \pm 2.34$ larvae individuals) (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Average (mean±S.E.) total mortality (expressed as a sum of consumed prey and attack prey) of prey (*Chironomus sp. larvae*) per experimental arena with the mesopredator – round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*). Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals around mean estimates. Treatments: C, control treatment (no stimuli); VIS, visual treatment (visual exposure to higher predator); CH, chemical treatment (exposure to kairomones/smell released by higher/top predator); VISCH, mixed treatment (simultaneous exposure to both visual and chemical stimuli).

Effects of treatments on three-type prey responses

Similarly to the results of GLMMs, the interaction between chemical × visual stimuli of the higher/top predator in modelling effects on frequencies of the ordinal prey responses by CLMMs was not significant ($X^2_{1=0.01}$, $p=0.91$), whereas only the effect of visual cues was significant ($X^2_1=28.73$; $p<0.001$) (Table 2). Comparisons of the probability of being consumed, attacked, or survived across different treatments revealed distinct patterns in relation to visual exposure of higher predator and/or chemical cues usage. Considering the initial total of 30 chironomid larvae, the highest probability of prey consumption was observed in the group without any external stimuli (C treatment), at $39.96\pm 2.94\%$ (Figure 5). A lower probability of larvae being eaten ($33.08\pm 4.16\%$) was observed in the CH treatment, and based on the 95% confidence intervals, this did not significantly differ from the control (C treatment) (Figure 5). Both treatments with visual stimuli (VIS, VISCH treatments) had significantly lower probabilities compared to the other tested groups, i.e. $17.25\pm 2.85\%$ in the VIS treatment and $13.41\pm 2.25\%$ in the VISCH treatment. The latter two treatments did not differ significantly from each other (Figure 5).

From sight to smell: does the visual and olfactory exposure to higher predator mitigate feeding activity in invasive round goby Neogobius melanostomus?

Table 2. Cumulative link mixed model (CLMM) of predicting prey status (*Chironomus sp.* larvae; consumed, attacked, survived) depending on treatment, i.e. visual predator exposure (Visual), predator scent (Chemical), and their interaction (Visual × Chemical). The random effects include individual fish observations (OBS_ID) and main arena consisting of both experimental arenas together (Arena_1), with respective variance components. The marginal and conditional R² values represent the variance explained by the fixed effects and the total model, respectively.

Predictors	Prey.status			Prey.status		
	Odds Ratios	CI	p	Odds Ratios	CI	p
Attacked/Consumed	0.66	0.51–0.85	0.001	0.67	0.52–0.85	0.001
Consumed/Survived	0.80	0.62–1.04	0.092	0.81	0.64–1.03	0.083
Visual[1]	3.13	1.83–5.34	<0.001	3.19	2.12–4.80	<0.001
Chemical [1]	1.32	0.81–2.15	0.259	1.35	0.91–1.98	0.132
Visual[1] × Chemical[1]	1.05	0.46–2.38	0.907			
Random Effects						
δ ²	3.29			3.29		
T ₀₀	0.90 _{OBS_ID}			0.90 _{OBS_ID}		
	0.41 _{Arena_1}			0.42 _{Arena_1}		
ICC	0.29			0.29		
N	216 _{OBS_ID}			216 _{OBS_ID}		
	109 _{Arena_1}			109 _{Arena_1}		
Observations	6480			6480		
Marginal R ² / Conditional R ²	0.072/0.338			0.072 0.338		

The highest survival rate was in the VISCH treatment, at 79.80±3.21%. This was significantly higher than the probability of survival in C treatment (55.31±3.02%), and CH treatment, respectively (62.49±4.39%; Figure 5).

Figure 5. Probability of tested prey (*Chironomus sp. larvae*) to be consumed by the mesopredator (*Neogobius melanostomus*) or to survive based on presence of higher/top predator-derived stimuli. Data shown as mean \pm SE. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals. Treatments: C, control treatment (no stimuli); VIS, visual treatment (visual exposure to higher/top predator); CH, chemical treatment (exposure to kairomones/smell released by higher predator); VISCH, mixed treatment (simultaneous exposure to both visual and chemical stimuli). Letters (a, b) denote the significant differences between treatments for the given prey status ($p < 0.05$).

The lowest attack/injury rate probability of the tested prey by the mesopredator was observed in the VISCH treatment, at $2.42 \pm 0.36\%$, significantly lower than $4.73 \pm 0.31\%$ in the C treatment and $4.42 \pm 0.37\%$ in the CH treatment (Figure 6). While the VIS treatment had the second-lowest probability ($2.95 \pm 0.41\%$), it did not significantly differ from the VISCH treatment, as their confidence intervals overlap (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Probability of the tested prey (*Chironomus* sp. Larvae) being attacked/injured by the mesopredator (*Neogobius melanostomus*) within the different treatments. Data shown as mean \pm SE. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals. Treatments: C, control treatment (no stimuli); VIS, visual treatment (visual exposure to higher/top predator); CH, chemical treatment (exposure to kairomones/smell released by higher predator); VISCH, mixed treatment (simultaneous exposure to both visual and chemical stimuli). Letters (a, b) denote the significant differences between treatments for the given prey status ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Visual cues and predator-prey interactions

Our study confirmed the responsiveness of the invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) as a mesopredator in the invaded areas to the presence of a higher/top native predator. However, the observed response, which was manifested by reduced feeding activity of the mesopredator and decreased total prey mortality, appears to be primarily/solely influenced by visual cues, which seem to be considered the most important stimuli involved into the predator-prey interactions (Dill, 1974a,b; Webb, 1982; Mikheev et al., 2006; Marsh-Hunkin et al., 2013). Presented outcomes align with the numerous studies confirming the importance of visual stimuli as a main cue in predator-prey interaction and local risk recognition (Fuiman, 1993; Landeira-Dabarca et al., 2019), including other gobiids relying heavily on visual information in multiple ways, such as predator detection (Utne-Palm, 2001), cognitive decision making (Ranucci et al., 2024) or habitat selection and mating (Lehtonen and Lindström, 2004; Yavno and Corkum, 2010).

Even though our study confirmed the prevalence of visual sensory cues in round goby risk detection, we cannot exclude the possibility that the observed response was triggered solely by an unknown motile object (not explicitly associated with danger), rather than by recognising a well-known predator. Previous research shows that fish often respond to general predator cues such as movement and size, associating the risk with the moving object rather than identifying a predator species per se (Tang et al., 2017). This response often requires the presence of chemical cues to associate the stimulus with danger (Chivers and Smith, 1998; Wisenden and Harter, 2001). Furthermore, many fish species, such as the Eurasian minnow *Phoxinus phoxinus* (Linnaeus 1758), exhibit behaviours related to predator recognition, such as inspection—where prey approach a predator to better recognize it and gather information about its behaviour (Magurran and Pitcher, 1987). However, this potential reaction was limited in our experimental design (despite the close proximity of the tanks; 1–2 mm), as both fish species were stocked separately. Consequently, the round goby's response to the higher predator might have been driven by novelty or general features rather than specific recognition of the perch as a threat. On the other hand, a study on *Chromis viridis* (Cuvier, 1830) (Karplus et al., 1982) demonstrated that specific phenotypic characteristics of piscivorous fish can elicit anti-predatory responses in prey compared to non-piscivorous species. This suggests that fish may associate certain features, such as the predator's face, with overall danger and fear (Karplus and Algom, 1981). However, such responses appear species-specific, as object shape has not been consistently shown to influence predator recognition in fathead minnows *Pimephales promelas* Rafinesque, 1820 (Wisenden and Harter, 2001). Overall, considering the ecological relevance of perch as a predator of the round goby, particularly at the size used in our study (Rakauskas et al., 2013; Mikl et al., 2017b), and their co-occurrence in the source locality (Janáč et al., 2019), we expected that some level of recognition would already have been established. We believe that this, together with the experimental design adjustments (proximity, aquarium space, type and size of the predator) to maximise visibility and exposure, likely ensured effective predator recognition and relevant outcomes.

Moreover, the results raise questions about whether the round goby fully utilizes its ability to detect visual risk in natural environments, as our experiment was conducted during the day (7:00–13:00) (Carman et al., 2006). While visual cues have been shown to play a role in round goby predation (e.g., *Gammarus* prey; Bergstrom and Mensinger, 2009), this sensory ability may not be fully employed due to the species' highest foraging activity occurring at night (Dubs and Corkum, 1996; Savino et al., 2007; Johnson et al., 2008; Christoffersen et al., 2019). Moreover, although the round goby can be active during the day as well focusing on the most abundant prey (Carman et al., 2006), its complete reliance on vision may be constrained by environmental conditions. The species inhabits various environments, favouring areas with lower water velocity (Roje et al., 2021a). In these habitats, factors such as turbidity (Sundin et al., 2010; Lunt and Smee, 2015; Leris et al., 2022) and habitat complexity (Fakan et al., 2023), including the presence of complex structures and sediments used by the round goby (Ray and Corkum, 2001), can reduce the effectiveness of visual perception and individual foraging behaviour (Schmitz et al., 2024). As a result, the ability to detect predation risks and mount appropriate antipredator responses may be weakened (Ferrari et al., 2010). Another reason for this limitation seems to be the general biometric characteristics of benthic species, where studies on other gobiids suggest that their maximum visual range is relatively short (Aksnes and Utne, 1997; Utne-Palm, 2002), which may similarly apply to the round goby, further limiting its reliance on vision in certain environments. Considering that visual cues are effective only at close proximity (Brown et al., 1997), and that increased turbidity conditions can further disturb and limit this distance (Vogel and Beauchamp, 1999; Zanghi et al., 2023), overall reliance can increase the risk of being attacked by local native predators.

Chemical cues role in round goby's risk detection

However, the nighttime foraging species generally rely more on chemical reception or mechanosensory tactile systems to avoid predator (Atta, 2013; Šmejkal et al., 2018; Nickles et al., 2020). Moreover, in ecosystems with frequent environmental changes, a multisensory detection approach is applied (Fischer, 2017), where both stimuli being equally important (Coleman and Rosenthal, 2006) or chemical cues even serve as a more universal and important sensory modality for predation risk estimation (Smith 1992; Brown, 2003; Wisenden, 2014). Therefore, based on the above facts, we originally expected to observe a similar or even greater reliance on chemical cues compared to visual cues, which are often considered additional support or backup when chemical information is unavailable or ambiguous (Hartman and Abrahams, 2000; Brown and Magnavacca, 2003). However, unlike other studies where fish reduced food intake in response to kairomones from sympatric predators (Jachner 1995, 1997; Kats and Dill, 1998), our study did not confirm this pattern. The round goby did not show response to chemical stimuli from a well-known higher/top predator, similarly to the frillfin goby *Bathygobius soporator* (Valenciennes, 1837), where predator odor also failed to evoke a reaction (Pereira et al., 2017). This may be explained by 48h starvation period applied to higher/top predator (Eurasian perch) prior to the experimental trial and absence of chemical cues derived from digested, attacked or scared prey. Studies by Brown and Magnavacca (2003) suggest that dietary chemical cues, including prey alarm cues, are the primary source and transmitter of information about potential predation risk. Similarly, research on glowlight tetras, *Hemigrammus erythrozonus* Durbin, 1909, confirmed that chemical inspection is influenced by the presence of alarm substances derived from a predator's diet (Brown and Godin, 1999). Moreover, this effect is evident even when fish are exposed to unfamiliar predators, as demonstrated by the fright reaction to unfamiliar predators that had been fed by prey containing alarm cues (Pettersson et al., 2000). On the other hand, studies proceeded on the crucian carp, *Carassius carassius* (Linnaeus, 1758) response to the predators has shown that there was no significant difference in the fright response of the tested fish while exposed to cues from hungry versus satiated northern pike, *Esox lucius* Linnaeus, 1758 (Pettersson et al., 2000). This suggests that the starvation status of the predator does not necessarily affect the prey's ability to detect and respond to the predator's presence. Instead, the observed outcomes may depend more on the capabilities of the mesopredator, i.e. the round goby. Notably, in our previous study, the round goby did not respond to dietary cues when tested with the local higher predator the European eel, *Anguilla anguilla* (Linnaeus, 1758), which had no effect on food intake or the digestion process in the round goby (Szydłowska et al., 2024). Although, since our primary objective was to assess how the presence of a local higher/top predator influences and potentially reduces feeding activity in the mesopredator, all round goby individuals were subjected to a starvation period to standardize hunger level. However, some researchers suggest that starved fish exhibit lower responsiveness to predators compared to those that have been fed (Gregory, 1993; Brown and Cowan, 2000), where satiation level was used to differentiate low- and high-risk scenarios, respectively (Hartman and Abrahams, 2000). Thus, we believe that a separate experimental design exclusively focused on fish perception, prioritizing both visual and chemical stimuli, should be implemented in future investigations while excluding additional variables to minimize potential confounding effects. Furthermore, Kelley and Magurran (2003) investigated both types of cues and found that visual recognition of predator relies mainly on inherent predispositions, whereas recognizing predator through smell typically necessitates previous encounters. Therefore, the importance of the learning process in shaping the round goby's responsiveness cannot be overlooked, as confirmed in other fishes where experience enhances and influences reactions (Larson and

McCormick, 2005; McLean et al., 2007; Holmes and McCormick, 2010), similarly to other taxa including crayfish (Kaur et al., 2023), or frogs (Ferrari and Chivers, 2008). Based on this, we believe that further exposure to the chemical cues could give some more pronounced results.

Multisensory exposure effect

Interestingly, in our present experiments involving simultaneous visual and chemical exposure, round goby individuals showed the greatest reduction in food consumption, along with an overall increase in the mortality of *Chironomus* sp. larvae. This aligns with findings from Mikheev et al. (2006), where YOY perch individuals were similarly affected under the influence of both stimuli from the higher predator. Since generally in nature, prey usually encounter information regarding local predatory risk in a more complex form, i.e. from multiple stimuli at once (Ward and Mehner, 2010; Manassa et al., 2013) which enhances their detection accuracy (Johnstone, 1996), the results obtained in our present experiment suggest the synergistic effect of the vision and olfaction in the round goby's predator response. While the previous studies confirmed that exposure to both cues together strengthens the overall anti-predatory response as observed in gobiids and other fish (McCormick and Manassa, 2008; Palacios et al., 2015), our statistical analyses did not confirm any significant interaction between two tested stimuli regarding their overall impact on the predatory behaviour of tested fish. Following that, given the behavioral feedback loop observed between smallmouth bass, *Micropterus dolomieu* Lacepède, 1802 and round goby, where the foraging actions of the higher predator influenced the goby's behaviour (Schmitz, 2024), we cannot also rule out the possibility that the behaviour of the Eurasian perch may have intensified the effect on prey consumption and attack rates of the round goby. Since prey response intensity is often driven by the predator's movement (Wisenden and Harter, 2001; Baerends et al., 1955), the locomotor activity of the higher predator in our study may have also influenced the results, due to the described interplay between vision and locomotion in fish reaction (Domenici, 2002). This is particularly relevant since our methodology involved live specimens, which do not ensure standardized or consistent behaviour, unlike studies that used controlled, artificial ethological techniques summarized by Rowland (1999), for instance, animation (Fischer et al., 2014, 2017). Therefore, the potential intensified fish activity observed in the VISCH treatment is supposed to additionally reduce the feeding activity following the threat-sensitive predator avoidance hypothesis, where the prey reaction intensity can appear in a graded manner and should match the overall danger level (Engström-Öst and Lehtiniemi, 2004; Ferrari and Chivers, 2006). Although this statement remains speculative, additional analyses, including higher predator activity, should be conducted for further validation. Overall, it is important to note that since no significant differences were found between the VIS and VISCH treatments in the probability of prey consumption, we cannot rule out the possibility that the tested fish perceived the mixed treatment in the same way as exposure to visual stimuli alone.

Fish size, foraging behavior and attack probability

Lastly, the coefficient estimates revealed discrepancies in round goby individual size, particularly smaller wet weights in the VISCH treatment, although the main analysis did not identify statistically significant differences among treatments. Given that fish size significantly affects foraging behaviour in round goby (Franta et al., 2023), smaller individuals tend to have reduced overall food intake as well as digestion capacity (Li et al., 2018). Therefore, it is essential to consider that fish size influences both feeding efficiency (Werner and Gilliam, 1984) and antipredatory responses, with smaller fish exhibiting stronger avoidance reactions

than larger individuals (Helfman, 1989). While size should not be viewed as the primary factor influencing feeding outcomes, it may contribute to the overall results observed in this study. As boldness and aggression are typically associated with greater food intake due to increased foraging and risk-taking (Sih et al., 2004; Stamps, 2007; Conrad et al., 2011) and given that round goby exhibit aggressive behaviours, including food and habitat competition (Charlebois et al., 1997; Savino et al., 2007; Church et al., 2017; Roje et al., 2021b), we hypothesised a higher likelihood of prey attacks by tested fish. However, our study revealed a significantly lower average attack probability compared to other ordinal prey responses. Considering that the average number of consumed prey was around half of the total provided, we cannot rule out the possibility that prey may have led to reduced aggression, reaching the saturation point where reduced hunger lead to decreased aggression, i.e. fewer attacks per unit (Morgan, 1988; Priyadarshana et al., 2006). Additionally, we raise the question of whether the attacked prey items (chironomid larvae) were the result of intentional predation or accidental injuries occurring during the foraging in the feeding zone, where prey were attached and provided to the fish. Furthermore, we cannot exclude the possibility that the partial immobilization of prey within the feeding zone affected higher attack rates, as previous studies have shown that immobilized amphipod prey are consumed more successfully by native counterparts than by invasive round goby (Błońska et al., 2016). In general, our results are consistent with studies modelling the functional response in round goby, which found that attack rate was significantly reduced by cues, including predator odour and alarm signals from conspecifics (Franta et al., 2024). Additionally, the fish tested in our studies belonged to the middle size group, corresponding to the most abundant size cohort in the invaded areas of the Elbe R., which exhibited the lowest attack success rates (Franta et al., 2023). This comparison may provide another possible explanation for our results.

Conclusions

Overall, our study confirmed the non-consumptive effects of a higher/top predator upon the round goby as a mesopredator, as the presence of Eurasian perch reduced the predatory efficiency of the round goby. While previous research has demonstrated that direct predation by Eurasian perch on round goby is common (Almqvist et al., 2010; Madenjian et al., 2011; Oesterwind et al., 2017), its impact on goby populations appears to be minimal (Liversage et al., 2017). Given that a complete eradication of the invasive round goby is not feasible (Kornis et al., 2012), our study supports the potential for habitat restoration to mitigate the effects of invasive species (Olden et al., 2004), especially since mesopredator benefits from the absence of higher/top predator's suppression (Ritchie and Johnson, 2009; Gordon et al., 2015; Palacios et al., 2016), as confirmed by our findings too. Following that, our results indicate that the presence of higher/top predators can reduce local pressure on macrozoobenthos (Henseler et al., 2021), and may help to alleviate competition with native fish species (Bergstrom and Mensinger 2008; Staněk, 2024). However, it's important to note that the invasive round goby as a mesopredator still maintained relatively high levels of predation throughout the experiment, despite the significant effect of the higher/top predator presence. The observed behavior of the round goby indicates its overall boldness, which allows it to successfully exploit available food resources (Behrens et al., 2020) and aligns with findings from Croy and Hughes (1991), suggesting that hungry fish will forage from 'dangerous sources' if the potential rewards outweigh the risks.

Additionally, our findings underscore the prominence of visual stimuli in the sensory hierarchy of the round goby to recognize its predator, where a combination of both types of stimuli together seems to provide the most potent response. The lack of a clear response to

chemical stimuli and uncertain reliance on vision in natural habitats suggest that round goby may adapt through trade-offs between foraging and time spent in shelter, whereas higher/top predator presence could potentially cause shifts in other behavioural and activity patterns as well. We aim to explore these dynamics further in future studies, including video analysis, to provide deeper insights into these behavioural adaptations.

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CHAPTER 5

GENERAL DISCUSSION

ENGLISH SUMMARY

CZECH SUMMARY

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS

TRAINING AND SUPERVISION PLAN DURING THE STUDY

CURRICULUM VITAE

General discussion

Prior the general discussion part it is important to state the major outcomes of particular research related chapters.

Chapter 2: Gut evacuation rate as a tool for revealing feeding patterns in the invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) under different feeding modes, food types and temperatures

- Temperature had a significant effect on the evacuation rates in round goby, with high food processing maintained even at lower temperatures (*Pisidium* sp.).
- Contrary to expectations, the highest evacuation rate and the fastest food processing were observed when round goby were fed hard-bodied prey (*Pisidium* sp.).
- Round goby individuals fed continuously exhibited much faster evacuation rates compared to those with fed only once.
- The potential superiority over the native species/counterparts in the food processing efficiency seems to be highly dependent on the used prey type.

Chapter 3: Risk perception: chemical stimuli in predator detection and feeding behaviour of the invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*

- Exposure to smell of the higher predator and alarm cues from conspecifics did not affect the feeding activity and evacuation rates in the round goby as a mesopredator in the invaded ecosystems.
- The lack of response to chemical cues can be considered another trait possibly associated with the round goby boldness, which enhances successful exploitation of food resources when entering new ecosystems, regardless of local higher predator presence.
- The round goby exhibited relatively high evacuation rates, when compared to native analogue, such as ruffe *Gymnocephalus cernua* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Chapter 4: From sight to smell: does the visual and olfactory exposure to higher predator mitigate feeding activity in invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*?

- Exposure to higher predator presence affects the feeding activity of round goby as a mesopredator.
- Feeding activity was significantly affected in both treatments with a visual exposure to higher predators, resulting in a lower number of consumed prey.
- The round goby did not respond to predator chemical stimuli only.
- The round goby remained efficient at preying throughout the experiment.

While investigating temperature as a major environmental factor affecting evacuation rates (Sweka et al., 2004; Gillum et al., 2012; Horstman, 2020), our studies confirmed the significant impact of this variable on gut content loss over time in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*). We hypothesised that the round goby individuals tested at higher temperatures (20 °C) would exhibit much higher evacuation rates, as indicated by most studies (Singh-Renton and Bromley, 1999; Legler et al., 2010; Stehlik et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2015). This hypothesis is based on the understanding that metabolic processes, including digestive enzyme activities (Persson, 1979, 1981; dos Santos and Jobling, 1995) and feeding rate (Brett, 1979; Kestemont and Baras, 2001), which are regulated by evacuation rate (Hedden et al., 2021), generally increase with temperature as expected for ectotherm animals as fishes are. In contrast to our expectations, the obtained results have shown different patterns, highly dependent on the type of tested prey, confirming overall importance

of the interaction between tested factors, as well as suggesting the overall predominance of the structural and biotic factors importance over the temperature. As presented in the **Chapter 2**, only the round goby individuals fed by the amphipod prey (the killer shrimp – *Dikerogammarus villosus*) were reported with the higher evacuation rate at the typical summer temperature (20 °C) in the invaded ecosystems of the Elbe River where the studied individuals came from. However, the round goby which ate the mollusc prey (*Pisidium* sp.), maintain higher evacuation rate at the typical autumn temperature (14 °C), respectively. This is in contradiction to our expectations. The summer temperatures (20–24 °C) in the native distribution range of the round goby, the molluscs are the most important and prevalent prey type in the diet (Demchenko and Tkachenko, 2017) and the metabolic rate is even up to six times higher than in the winter as reported by Skazkina and Kostyuhenko (1968). Even the difference between the temperatures tested in our studies was not so big (only 6 °C), we still expected to observe proportionally lower evacuation rate to these differences. Therefore, one possible explanation for the observed higher evacuation rate at the lower temperature for mollusc prey could be the overall high environmental tolerance exhibited by the round goby (Moskal'kova, 1996; Charlebois et al., 2001; Silva et al., 2019; Christensen et al., 2021), which maintains active feeding activity throughout the season, including the winter period (Dashinov and Uzunova, 2020). This aligns with other studies that did not confirm significant differences in attack rate and handling time between 20 and 25 °C (Gebauer et al., 2018). However, since the highest evacuation rate was observed in fish fed by hard-bodied clams, this suggests that while overall temperature is an important driver for all biological processes (Brown et al., 2004) and affects predator-prey interactions (Pereira et al., 2010), its effect might be attenuated by other factors. The seasonal effectiveness of prey use and diet is not only temperature-dependent but also multifactorial, relying on the physical characteristics of the prey and its seasonal availability (Didenko et al., 2017). However, in addition to the studied evacuation rate, it appears to be beneficial to determine the efficiency of food digestion depending on the water temperature itself as well. This issue was not addressed in our studies and would thus represent one of the topics for further research. Specifically, future experiments might focus on analyzing digested material at the end of the intestine, as digestive efficiency may vary despite similar excretion rates, potentially due to temperature-related changes in enzymatic activity (Volkoff and Rønnestad, 2020).

Following that, results presented in Chapter 2 revealed the significant effect of the prey type and its body structure on the gut evacuation rate in round goby. Notably, there were discrepancies between two hard-bodied prey types. Fish fed with the bivalve *Pisidium* sp. exhibited the fastest evacuation rate, while amphipod prey was digested and evacuated slowest, taking 36 hours for gut clearance. Although the observation of faster evacuation rate for *Pisidium* sp. compared to soft-bodied prey (*Chironomus* sp.) contradicts many previous studies (Jones, 1974; Singh-Renton and Bromley, 1999; Temming and Herrmann, 2003), we believe this pattern seems to be inherent for round goby, as this species is well adapted to feed on bivalve prey by crushing it with molariform teeth (Ghedotti et al., 1995; Andraso et al., 2011a), which enables the exploitation of hard-shelled prey (Angradi, 2018) and is accelerated by presence of suitable digestive enzymes (Aarnio and Bonsdorff, 1997). We believe that this feature, compensating for the simplified digestive tract functions (Geevarghese, 1983; Barton, 2007), contributed to much faster evacuation rate in comparison to individuals fed by other food types. However, it is essential to acknowledge that this observation could change within the different tested round goby size classes, as the evacuation rate highly depends on the predator size (Flowerdew and Grove, 1979; dos Santos and Jobling, 1995; Seyhan et al. 2020) and prey size (Bagge, 1977; dos Santos and Jobling, 1995; Andersen, 1998). Given these, including the ontogenetic changes in morphology (Marsden et al. 1996; Andraso et al. 2011a;

Števove and Kováč, 2016), some bivalves can remain as intact or crushed form based on these (Andraso et al., 2011b), respectively. Therefore, different size classes of the round goby (i.e., >55 mm and <75 mm) should undergo further and more precise investigations. As in the study by Mack and Andraso (2015), the residence time of dreissenids in the gut of the round goby (body size of 82–88 mm) was less than 48 hours, whereas in our study, clams were evacuated in 16 hours after they were eaten. Moreover, Franta et al. (2023) found that medium-sized round goby individuals had the highest feeding rate, followed by large and small individuals. Hence, we could expect a similar dependency when it comes to the evacuation rate in our results. The observed prolonged digestion of the amphipod prey seemed to be attributed to the thick and flexible robust exoskeleton resistance (Błońska et al., 2015). The maximisation of the nutrient absorption, such as fatty acids (Maazouzi et al., 2007), can be also the reason for longer digestion as the overall rich-amphipod diet was confirmed to contribute better growth and body condition (Polačik et al., 2009). A similar pattern can be observed with the highly nutritionally valuable chironomid larvae (Sushchik et al., 2006). The slowest evacuation rate observed in non-continuous feeding may be then attributable to prolonged satiety, serving as an adaptation during species' transport and active dispersal to new localities with limited food availability.

Moreover, we found that continual feeding led to significantly higher evacuation rate, with food being processed up to 10 times faster compared to non-continuous feeding events. The observed accelerated evacuation can be attributed to intensified metabolic activity (O'Connor et al., 2000) and mechanical factors, where subsequent food intake pushes the digestive content through the gut more quickly (Riche et al., 2004). These observations align with previous studies indicating that increased food availability leads to higher evacuation rate (Noble, 1973; Elliott, 1975; Jones, 1974; Tekinay, 2003), potentially resulting in higher feeding rate due to the regulation of these processes (Hedden et al., 2021). Additionally, the tested effect of the prey availability can be potentially linked to different invasion stages of the population. In the early stages (pioneering populations), abundant food supply (reflected as continual feeding) allows the exploitation of a wide range of accessible resources (Iacarella et al., 2015; Burton et al., 2010; Raby et al., 2010). In contrast, established populations with higher densities face restricted resource availability (parallel to non-continuous feeding mode), leading to increased intraspecific competition and reduced feeding efficiency (Brownscombe and Fox, 2012; Azour et al., 2015).

Given the aforementioned observations from our studies, and considering other research conducted under continual feeding regimes simulating natural conditions (as reviewed in Bromley, 1994; Tekinay et al., 2003), it is evident that the potential superiority in food processing among species is prey-type dependent. For instance, compared to studies on the ruffe (*Gymnocephalus cernua*), the round goby evacuates chironomid larvae almost three times faster under similar thermal conditions (Hölker and Temming, 1996). This suggests a potential competitive advantage for the round goby when sharing the same niche, possibly contributing to the temporary decline (Rakauskas et al., 2013; Ramler and Keckeis, 2019) or even collapse (Jůza et al., 2018) of native species after the arrival of the round goby. Conversely, the round goby seems to be less efficient at digesting and processing amphipod prey (total gut clearance within 36 hours) compared to the native bottom-dwelling analogue - European bullhead (*Cottus gobio*), which co-occur in localities within the Elbe River (Lagrué and Bollache, 2006; Janáč et al., 2019). Thus, based on our study, the round goby can be potentially more successful competitors depending on the locally available prey. However, it is important to note that the efficiency of food resource exploitation depends not only on the rate of food processing but also on factors such as capture efficiency and foraging behaviour (Gebauer, 2018; Franta, 2021; Franta, 2023), as well as other behavioural traits like higher

aggression during competitive interactions (Balshine et al., 2005; Groen et al., 2012; Leino and Mensinger, 2015; Borcherding et al., 2019; Roje et al., 2021).

Chapter 3 representing the study where we decided to include in and test evacuation rate as well as food consumption probability while the round goby as a mesopredator was exposed to the higher predator (the European eel) odours as well as the alarm cues derived from scared and injured conspecifics. Contrary to expectations, where Belanger and Corkum (2003) underlines the crucial role of chemosensory signalling in the round goby survival, our tested fish did not exhibit significant changes in consumption probabilities and no differences were observed in the evacuation rate in response to both types of chemical cues. Overall, the observed indifference of the round goby to the chemical risk cues might be explained by the species' requirement for certain concentrations of alarm signals, regulated by species-specific thresholds (Atema, 1980; Jónsson, 1980), or by a diminished sensitivity of the round goby to solely alarm cues compared to other gobiids (Kłosiński et al., 2022). Previous studies have shown that a magnitude of fish reactions to chemical stimuli increases with the concentration of cues (Zhao and Chivers, 2005; Zhao et al., 2006). Therefore, it is also possible that different methodologies in alarm cue preparation and their application frequency might yield varying responses (Lönnstedt and McCormick, 2011; Chivers et al., 2013). On the other hand, another possibility is that the round goby may exhibit physiological reactions to the perception of alarm cues, such as increased respiratory responses (Pütys et al., 2015) or elevated blood cortisol levels (Galli et al., 2023). However, none of these changes seems to be reflected in the overall behavioral response of the frightened fish. Despite this, the round goby maintained a high evacuation rate similar to those observed within the **Chapter 2**, suggesting that the feeding efficiency of the round goby is not easily disrupted by predator presence. The observed trait can be linked with the well-studied boldness (Myles-Gonzalez et al., 2015; Behrens et al., 2020; Ericsson et al., 2021) and thus ability to continue exploiting feeding resources irrespectively to potential threats. This may facilitate the invasion process of the non-native predators within the newly invaded ecosystems irrespectively to the local predators and provide a competitive advantage in new environments comparing to other local species, aiding their invasiveness (Ylönen et al., 2007), and it seems that this also applies to the round goby.

Since we did not obtain any significant effect of the predator odour and the alarm cues derived from the conspecifics (**Chapter 3**), we decided to continue the further investigation, including using another higher local predator and comparing the effect of chemical and visual perception. The results obtained in **Chapter 4** showed that the tested round goby individuals still did not respond to the chemical cues derived from the higher predator, particularly the European perch (*Perca fluviatilis*). This is in line with the commonly observed pattern where salmonids are the only fish group that can recognize smell of higher predators (Berejikian et al., 2003; Vilhunen and Hirvonen, 2003), while in majority of fish the predator-derived kairomones (deprived of cues originated from prey) did not initiate any reaction (Utne-Palm 2001; Arvigo et al., 2019). This additionally excludes our previous assumption that the lack of response could be higher-predator species dependent, confirming that regardless of the used species, the round goby still did not show any reaction. Thus, we can exclude the possibility that the choose of predator could potentially affect the results, as both predatory species (perch and eel) are recognized to actively prey on the round goby (Almqvist et al., 2010; Rakauskas et al., 2013; Emde et al., 2014; Mikl et al., 2017). Moreover, they co-occur in the monitored localities in the Elbe River where the tested round goby individuals came from (Buřič et al., 2020) and thus a certain experience level of the chemical perception in the round goby would already have been established. Since the round goby was exposed to a sufficient concentration of water with the predator smell, it is likely that in both cases (**Chapter 3**

and Chapter 4), the recognition of the higher predator via kairomones requires learning and repetitive experience, as shown in many other studies (Mirza and Chivers, 2001; Kristensen and Closs, 2004; McLean et al., 2007).

On the other hand, a certain insensitivity of the round goby to the predator chemical cues, besides indicating a high threshold for cue detection, could also suggest the necessity of visual cues to trigger and modulate a full anti-predator response, as observed in other fish species including gobiids as well (Utne-Palm 2001; Manassa et al., 2013). However, the results presented in **Chapter 4** did not confirm an interaction between both stimulus types (visual versus chemical cues) while testing consumption probability, which is reflected in the counts of eaten prey. Given that, observed reduced prey counts seem to be exclusively affected by visual exposure to the predator rather than by both cue types together, as observed by Kelley and Magurran (2003), Lehtiniemi (2005), McCormick and Manassa (2008). This suggests that visual detection of the predator is crucial for gobiids, highlighting its relative importance in their sensory hierarchy (Utne, 1997; Utne-Palm, 2001; Brown, 2003). Following that, similarly to the findings of the Swanbrow Becker and Gabor (2012), it appears that lacking or reducing visual input hampers the round goby's overall response and risk detection efficiency. However, it is important to note that this reliance on vision may not always be beneficial in practice. While visual cues provide reliable, immediate, and direct information (Helfman, 1989), they require much closer proximity to the risk source (Stephenson, 2016). Additionally, environmental conditions such as habitat complexity, light level, and turbidity can significantly limit the effectiveness of visual predator detection (Bryer et al., 2000; Hartman and Abrahams, 2000; Alemadi and Wisenden, 2002). Moreover, reliance over the visual cues in case of the round goby seems to be questionable since the main foraging activity and feeding behaviour are recognised as a nocturnal one (Dubs and Corkum, 1996; Johnson et al., 2008).

Conclusions

Our research initiates a first step into the comprehensive approach to quantify consumption and thus to evaluate the predatory impact of the round goby in areas they have colonised. By integrating laboratory-derived gut evacuation rate with field gut samples, following methodologies similar to those of Bernreuther et al. (2009), and calculating daily consumption based on Elliot and Persson (1978), we can assess a more accurate consumption rate of this highly invasive fish. Coupled with data on macrozoobenthic assemblage densities, this provides extensive insights into predator-prey dynamics and consumption patterns of invasive species.

Given the environmental conditions analysed in these studies, including primary food resource types, seasonal temperatures, and diverse prey availability scenarios, we propose that our findings are applicable beyond the local context. Monitoring of the local populations can aid in assessing predatory pressure and consumption rates of the round goby at both individual and population levels in various colonised regions. Our results contribute to understanding the consumption rate of the round goby in different ecosystems. Future research should emphasise studying evacuation rate to refine estimates of prey utilisation and predator efficiency.

Our research demonstrated the significant influence of temperature, prey type, and prey availability on the gut evacuation rate in round gobies, while also uncovering the complexities and importance of interactions among these factors. Our study highlights that round gobies process food more efficiently when feeding on chironomids and molluscs, potentially exerting greater predatory pressure on these prey types in invaded areas. Conversely, although amphipods are preferred in certain localities, such as the Elbe River (Szydłowska et al., 2024),

our findings suggest that the predation efficiency and overall pressure on them are likely lower.

Additionally, the presented Ph.D. thesis offers novel insights into the feeding efficiency of the round goby, examining how local predation risk affects foraging and consumption behaviour of the round goby in the presence of the higher predators. This can enhance our understanding of early risk detection and the significance of specific stimulants, addressing gaps in current knowledge.

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English summary

Invasive species pose a significant threat to ecosystems worldwide, often disrupting food webs, altering species interactions, and reducing biodiversity. The round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*), a highly invasive fish species originating from the Ponto-Caspian region, is one such invader that has rapidly spread across freshwater systems in Europe and North America. This doctoral thesis investigates the impact of the round goby in freshwater ecosystems, focusing on its feeding behaviour and the application of gut evacuation rate methods to estimate its predatory pressure. Additionally, it examines how the presence of native predators, such as the European eel and European perch, might influence the round goby's overall feeding activity, potentially mitigating its impact. Through a series of experiments, we examined how the round goby's digestion and feeding proceeding rates, food consumption, and responsiveness to predator cues (both chemical and visual) may contribute to its success as an invasive species and its effects on local biodiversity.

Chapter 2 investigates the round goby's gut evacuation rates when feeding on different prey types (native freshwater clams, invasive amphipods, and chironomid larvae), under varying temperatures and feeding scenarios. The results show that round goby processes food faster when prey is continuously available, with the highest evacuation rates observed for clams. This suggests significant predatory pressure on chironomids and molluscs, which could lead to resource depletion and competition with other species relying on these prey. Interestingly, stomach content analysis from monitored localities indicates a shift in prey preferences, particularly towards the invasive amphipod *Dikerogammarus villosus*. Although gobies showed a preference for amphipods, the slower evacuation rate for this prey suggests that overall predatory pressure may be lower compared to faster-processed prey, such as molluscs and chironomids.

Chapter 3 examined whether chemical cues from a higher native predator, the European eel (*Anguilla anguilla*), would alter the round goby's feeding behaviour. Surprisingly, no significant differences were found in food consumption or gut evacuation rates when gobies were exposed to predator-derived chemical signals. This lack of response suggests a degree of boldness in the round goby, which may contribute to its competitive success in invaded ecosystems, as it continues to feed efficiently despite potential predation threats.

In **Chapter 4**, the focus shifted to understanding how both visual and chemical cues from predators impact the round goby's foraging behaviour. The study found that visual cues significantly affected prey consumption, leading to increased prey mortality, while chemical cues alone did not have a significant effect. Interestingly, there was no interaction between the visual and chemical stimuli, where at the same time exposure to both stimuli simultaneously provided the most reduced prey consumption. The findings indicate that visual detection plays a crucial role in decisive behaviour of the round goby's response to predation risk together with the presence of chemical cue. The overall adaptation of this behaviour in natural settings—considering the round goby's nocturnal habits and environmental challenges like turbidity—raises questions about the effectiveness of this strategy in the wild.

Together, these studies highlight the round goby's resilience and efficiency as an invasive species, with high predatory pressure on benthic invertebrates and a limited response to native predators' chemical cues. This research underscores the importance of further investigating predator-prey dynamics in invaded ecosystems to better understand the round goby's ecological impact and inform management strategies aimed at preserving local biodiversity. Additionally, the gut evacuation rate estimates from these studies will serve as a base for further calculations of consumption rates in combination with the samples from the field, helping to quantify the round goby's predatory impact on specific macroinvertebrate assemblages.

Czech summary

Invasní druhy představují významnou hrozbu pro ekosystémy po celém světě, často narušují potravní sítě, mění interakce mezi druhy a snižují biodiverzitu. Hlaváč černoústý (*Neogobius melanostomus*), vysoce invazní druh ryby pocházející z ponto-kaspické oblasti, je jedním z těchto invazních druhů, který se rychle rozšířil do sladkovodních systémů v Evropě a Severní Americe. Tato disertační práce zkoumá vliv hlaváče černoústého na sladkovodní ekosystémy se zaměřením na jeho potravní chování a aplikaci metod pro stanovení rychlosti vyprazdňování žaludku, které slouží k odhadu jeho predančního tlaku. Dále práce zkoumá, jak přítomnost původních predátorů, jako je úhoř říční (*Anguilla anguilla*) a okoun říční (*Perca fluviatilis*), může ovlivnit celkovou krmnou aktivitu hlaváče a potenciálně zmírnit jeho negativní dopady. V rámci série experimentů jsme zkoumali, jak rychlost trávení a zpracování potravy, konzumace potravy a reakce na podněty detekující přítomnost predátora (chemické i vizuální) přispívají k úspěšnosti hlaváče jako invazního druhu a jak ovlivňují místní biodiverzitu.

Kapitola 2 se zabývá rychlostí vyprazdňování žaludku hlaváče při konzumaci různých druhů potravy (původní sladkovodní mlži, invazní blešivci a larvy pakomárů) při různých teplotách a scénářích dostupnosti potravy. Výsledky ukazují, že hlaváči tráví potravu rychleji, když je neustále dostupná, přičemž nejvyšší rychlost vyprazdňování byla zaznamenána při konzumaci mlžů. To naznačuje, že hlaváči vyvíjejí výrazný predanční tlak na pakomáry a mlže, což může vést k vyčerpání zdrojů a konkurenci s jinými druhy, které jsou na těchto zdrojích závislé. Zajímavé je, že analýza obsahu žaludku z monitorovaných lokalit ukázala posun v preferencích potravy, zejména směrem k invaznímu blešivci *Dikerogammarus villosus*. Přestože hlaváči vykazovali preferenci pro blešivce, pomalejší rychlost vyprazdňování u tohoto druhu naznačuje, že celkový predanční tlak může být nižší ve srovnání s rychleji zpracovávanou potravou, jako jsou mlži a pakomáři.

Kapitola 3 se zabývala otázkou, zda chemické podněty od vyššího původního predátora, úhoře říčního (*Anguilla anguilla*), změní potravní chování hlaváče. Překvapivě nebyly zjištěny žádné významné rozdíly v konzumaci potravy ani v rychlosti vyprazdňování žaludku, když byli hlaváči vystaveni chemickým signálům predátora. Tato nedostatečná reakce naznačuje určitou míru odvážnosti hlaváče (schopnosti podstupovat vyšší riziko), což by mohlo přispívat k jeho úspěšnosti v konkurenčním prostředí, protože nadále efektivně konzumuje potravu navzdory potenciálním hrozbám ze strany predátorů.

Kapitola 4 se zaměřila na pochopení, jak vizuální a chemické podněty predátorů ovlivňují potravní chování hlaváče. Studie zjistila, že vizuální podněty významně ovlivnily konzumaci potravy a vedly k vyšší úmrtnosti kořisti, zatímco samotné chemické podněty neměly významný vliv. Zajímavé je, že kombinace vizuálních a chemických podnětů nevykazuje žádnou interakci, ačkoli současná expozice oběma typům podnětů vedla k nejnižší konzumaci potravy. Tyto výsledky naznačují, že vizuální detekce hraje klíčovou roli v reakci hlaváče na riziko predace. Nicméně s ohledem na noční aktivitu hlaváče a environmentální faktory, jako je zákal vody a limitace světelnými podmínkami, vyvstávají otázky ohledně účinnosti této strategie v přirozeném prostředí.

Předložené studie společně zdůrazňují odolnost a efektivitu hlaváče jako invazního druhu, který vykazuje vysoký predanční tlak na bentické bezobratlé a omezenou reakci na chemické podněty původních predátorů. Výsledky výzkumu podtrhují důležitost dalšího zkoumání dynamiky vztahů predátor-kořist v invadovaných ekosystémech, aby bylo možné lépe porozumět ekologickým dopadům hlaváče a navrhnout strategie řízení zaměřené na ochranu místní biodiverzity. Navíc odhady rychlosti vyprazdňování žaludku získané v těchto studiích budou sloužit jako základ pro další výpočty míry konzumace ve spojení se vzorky z terénu, což pomůže kvantifikovat predanční dopad hlaváče na konkrétní společenstva makrozoobentosu.

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List of publications

Peer-reviewed journals with IF

- Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Franta, P., Let, M., Mikšová, V., Buřič, M., Drozd, B., 2024. Risk perception: chemical stimuli in predator detection and feeding behaviour of the invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*. *Biology-Basel* 13, 406. (IF 2024 = 3.6)
- Szydłowska, N.Z.**, M., Let, Franta, P., Buřič, M., Worischka, S., Richter, L., Drozd, B., 2024. Gut evacuation rate as a tool for revealing feeding patterns in the invasive round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*) under different feeding modes, food types and temperatures. *Aquatic Invasions* 19, 445–475. (IF 2023 = 2.2)
- Franta, P., Gebauer, R., Veselý, L., **Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Drozd, B., 2023. Size-dependent functional response of the round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*; implications for more accurate impact potential calculation. *Aquatic Invasions* 18, 507–520. (IF 2022 = 1.6)
- Franta, P., Gebauer, R., Veselý, L., Buřič, M., **Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Drozd, B., 2021. The invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus* as a potential threat to native crayfish populations. *Animals* 11, 2377. (IF2020 = 2.752)

Manuscripts

- Franta, P., **Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Kolář, V., Boukal, D., Gebauer, R., Drozd, B., 2024. The trade-off between foraging efficiency maximizing and predator avoidance in the round goby (*Neogobius melanostomus*): To be scared or fine? (Manuscript)
- Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Buřič, M., Let, M., Kubec, J., Drozd, B., 2024. From sight to smell: does the visual and olfactory exposure to higher predator mitigate feeding and activity in invasive round goby *Neogobius melanostomus*? (Manuscript)
- Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Let, M., Bláha, M., Buřič, M., Drozd, B., 2024. Diet composition and feeding preferences of invasive round goby and native European bullhead: Implications for macrozoobenthos communities in the Ploučnice River. (In preparation)
- Szydłowska, N.Z.**, Let, M., Avramović, M., Bláha, M., Buřič, M., Drozd, B., 2024. Size-selective predation on zooplankton by the invasive topmouth gudgeon (*Pseudorasbora parva*) under laboratory conditions. (In preparation)

Abstracts and conference proceedings

- Szydłowska, N.**, Let, M., Bláha, M., Buřič, M., Drozd, B., 2024. Macroinvertebrates under pressure: can the Ponto-Caspian invader affect them more than native? 4th Central European Symposium for Aquatic Macroinvertebrate Research – CESAMIR2024. July 7–12, 2024, Stará Lesná, Slovakia, p. 143.
- Szydłowska, N.**, Buřič, M., Let, M., Kubec, J., Drozd, B., 2023. The non-consumptive effect of higher predator upon food consumption in highly invasive mesopredator *Neogobius melanostomus*: the role of visual and olfactory stimuli in early predatory risk detection. 17th European Congress of Ichthyology. September 4–8, 2023, Prague, Czech Republic, p. 71.
- Buřič, M., Ložek, F., Kubec, J., Kuklina, I., Musil, M., Roje, S., **Szydłowska, N.**, Kouba, A., 2022. No way to get it out: the vain fight with signal crayfish in a small stream. 23rd Symposium of the International Association of Astacology, June 20–25, Hluboká nad Vltavou, Czech Republic, p. 17.

Training and supervision plan during study

Name	Natalia Zuzanna Szydłowska
Research department	Laboratory of Freshwater Ecosystems of FFPW
Supervisor	Bořek Drozd, Ph.D.
Period	October 2020 – March 2025
Ph.D. courses – Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters	
	Year
Toxicology focused on aquatic organisms	2020
Biostatistics	2020
Biological invasions in freshwater ecosystems	2021
Ecology of still and running waters	2021
Cycles of elements in aquatic ecosystems and their catchments	2021
Modern regression methods	2021
Design and analysis of ecological experiments	2021
Czech language exam	2022
English language exam (FCE)	2022
Scientific seminars	
	Year
Seminar days of RIFCH and FFPW	2021
	2022
	2023
	2024
International conferences	
	Year
Szydłowska, N. , Let, M., Bláha, M., Buřič, M., Drozd, B., 2024. Macroinvertebrates under pressure: can the Ponto-Caspian invader affect them more than native? 4 th Central European Symposium for Aquatic Macroinvertebrate Research – CESAMIR2024. July 7–12, 2024, Stará Lesná, Slovakia, p. 143.	2024
Szydłowska, N. , Buřič, M., Let, M., Kubec, J., Drozd, B., 2023. The non-consumptive effect of higher predator upon food consumption in highly invasive mesopredator <i>Neogobius melanostomus</i> : the role of visual and olfactory stimuli in early predatory risk detection. 17 th European Congress of Ichthyology. September 4–8, 2023, Prague, Czech Republic, p. 71.	2023
Buřič, M., Ložek, F., Kubec, J., Kuklina, I., Musil, M., Roje, S., Szydłowska, N. , Kouba, A., 2022. No way to get it out: the vain fight with signal crayfish in a small stream. 23 rd Symposium of the International Association of Astacology, June 20–25, 2022, Hluboká nad Vltavou, Czech Republic, p. 17.	2022
Foreign stays during Ph.D. study at RIFCH and FFPW	
	Year
Prof. Dr. Jost Borchering and Dr. Lisa Heermann, The Ecological Research Station Rees, Institute of Zoology - General Ecology, University of Cologne, Germany, this should be follow later by the rest of the text, ie. Predation o on non-indigenous invasive gobies by juvenile burbot <i>Lota lota</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2023
Projects and awards:	
	Year
Dean's Award for Best Presentation among Ph.D. candidates at the seminar	2022
ONE-YEAR Individual Grant; 082/2023/Z; Grant agency of the University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice (GAJU)	2023
Dean's Award for Best Presentation among Ph.D. candidates at the seminar	2024

Best Student Poster Prize; 4th Central European Symposium for Aquatic Macroinvertebrate Research (CESAMIR 2024) 2024

Pedagogical activities:	Year
Laboratory and field work sampling tutoring of students (Bc., Mgr.) in a range of 75 hours	2020–2024
Lecturing for the first-year students of Protection of Waters within the subject Ecology, FFPW USB, in a range of 4 hours	2022–2023
Assisting in practice excersises for students within the subject Culture of Mollusc and Crustaceans, FFPW USB, in a range of 15 hours	2023–2024
Consultant of the master thesis “Vliv hlaváče černoústého (<i>Neogobius melanostomus</i>) na potravní řetězec řeky Ploučnice” (Student: Pavel Staněk)	2023–2024
Leading the project entitled “Feeding behaviour and size-selective predation on zooplankton by the invasive topmouth gudgeon (<i>Pseudorasbora parva</i>) in laboratory conditions” (Student: Jacek Sadowski)	2024

Curriculum vitae

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Name: Natalia Zuzanna
Surname: Szydłowska
Title: M.Sc.
Born: 22nd February, 1994, Częstochowa, Poland
Nationality: Polish
Languages: Polish, English (B2 – FCE certificate), Czech
Contact: nszydlovska@frov.jcu.cz,

EDUCATION

2017–2019 M.Sc., Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, Department of Ecology and Zoology of Vertebrates, University of Łódź, Poland
2014–2017 B.Sc., Faculty of Biology and Environmental Protection, Department of Ecology and Zoology of Vertebrates, University of Łódź, Poland
2010–2013 II Liceum Ogólnokształcące im. Romualda Traugutta, Częstochowa, Poland

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

2020 – present Ph.D. student in Protection of aquatic ecosystems,, Faculty of Fisheries and Protection of Waters, University of South Bohemia, Ceske Budejovice, Czech Republic

COMPLETED COURSES

Toxicology focused on aquatic organisms, Biostatistics, Biological invasions in freshwater ecosystems, Ecology of still and running waters, Cycles of elements in aquatic ecosystems and their catchment, Modern regression methods, Design and analysis of ecological experiments, Czech language exam, English language exam (FCE)

SPECIALIZATION

Biological invasions in freshwater ecosystems

RESEARCH STAY AND COLLABORATIONS

01/03–31/05 2024 Prof. Dr. Jost Borcherding and Dr. Lisa Heermann, The Ecological Research Station Rees, Institute of Zoology - General Ecology, University of Cologne, Germany

PROJECTS, AWARDS, ETC.

2022 Dean's award for best presentation among Ph.D. candidates at the seminar
2023 ONE-YEAR Individual Grant; 082/2023/Z; Grant agency of the University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice (GAJU)
2024 Dean's award for best presentation among Ph.D. candidates at the seminar
2024 Best Student Poster Prize; 4th Central European Symposium for Aquatic Macroinvertebrate Research (CESAMIR 2024)

